

**Digital
Citizenship**

Digital Citizenship Model Course

Digital Citizenship Model Course

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Abstract	<p>This model course for the development of Digital Citizenship skills is a guideline designed to assist trainers and educators to introduce and organise training courses and non-formal educational activities for youngsters.</p> <p>It comprises 10 lesson plans supported by: course aim, competencies and area of knowledge, teaching syllabus, practical exercises, evaluation method, as well as the recognition system.</p> <p>By following this guideline and the recommended methods for teaching and assessment, trainers can enhance the existing training materials, to further deliver effective training to youth in the 10 digital domains essential for today’s digital world.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access and Inclusion • Learning and Creativity • Media and Information Literacy • Ethics and Empathy • Health and Wellbeing • e-Presence and Communications • Active Participation • Rights and Responsibilities • Privacy and Security • Consumer Awareness

	<p>The model shall not be seen as exhaustive, and the course designer is invited to adapt the time and educational materials in accordance with the trainees' level of understanding.</p> <p>The educational materials for the proposed lesson plans supported by course curricula, quizzes, case studies and exercises are available online via the e-learning platform: https://courses.trainingclub.eu/.</p>
Keywords	<p>Model course, Digital citizenship, Course plan, Online teaching methods, instructional design, Moodle, methodology, teaching methods, training, education, digital education, technology, digitalization, youth work, digital word, access and inclusion, learning and creativity, media and information literacy, ethics and empathy, health and wellbeing, e-presence and communication, active participation, rights and responsibilities, privacy and security, consumer awareness</p>

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Disclaimer

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Introduction

The purpose of the Digital citizenship model course is to assist trainers and educators to introduce and organize new training courses and enhance the existing training materials, to further deliver effective training to youth.

This model course is a guide comprising the recommended methods for teaching, assessment and expected time required for young people to develop their digital citizenship skills.

In order to use the model course, the trainer should review and adapt the course plan and detailed syllabus.

Adjustment of course objectives, scope and content may be necessary for the youth completing the course to develop appropriate digital citizenship skills.

Within the course plan, the course designers have indicated the time for completing each area of learning. However, the time can be adapted in accordance with the trainees' level of understanding.

Having adjusted the educational materials in such a manner to suit the trainees' level of understanding, the trainer should draw the lesson plans based on the detailed syllabus.

Within the international Erasmus Strategic Partnership, the research team proposes lessons plan and assessment tools for developing the digital citizenship skills of the young generation, in the 10 digital domains essential for today's digital world.

- Access and Inclusion
- Learning and Creativity
- Media and Information Literacy
- Ethics and Empathy
- Health and Wellbeing
- e-Presence and Communications
- Active Participation
- Rights and Responsibilities
- Privacy and Security
- Consumer Awareness.

The proposed lesson plans supported by the course curriculum, quizzes, case studies and exercises are available online via the e-learning platform: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>. Some of the activities are appropriate for reading and self-reflection, while others are designed to be facilitated in classrooms by trainers, requesting the active involvement of participants.

Course Plan Design

A typical course plan comprises a course outline with a list of competencies and areas of knowledge, a detailed teaching syllabus to achieve the training outcomes in accordance with Bloom’s taxonomy, practical exercises and evaluation method, as well as the recognition system.

With the intention to offer prospective trainers adaptable teaching materials, the following paragraphs laid down some guidelines for developing attractive and engaging lessons.

A. Course overview

Course description: *[This section describes the course aim and gives a short presentation of theoretical and practical concepts related to the subject. It includes a summary of what the course is meant to develop. In order to emphasize the relevance for the actual world, this section describes the main factors of motivation for deciding to run activities with youth.]*

Course structure: *[A detailed presentation of the structure with modules, exercises and case studies is designed to enable prospective trainers to adapt the course to the youth's level of understanding.]*

Essential questions: *[These are formulated to inspire teachers to start with the end in mind. The results are essential for both categories trainers and trainees]*

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 4 days • Weeks • Months
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-life situations • Daily tasks • Regular activities
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance • Necessity
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key knowledge • Skills

B. Statement of training methodology

Training methodology: *[This is an overview of the integration of instructional design methods, principles and processes; it can refer to the 5E of instruction, the ADDIE instructional model, as well as from the book the first principles of instruction of (Merril, D. 2002). This section explains the chosen teaching methods to be used throughout the course. For designing this section, the researches can take inspiration from the. MOOC Canvas and Instructional Design manual.]*

C. Course aims and objectives

Aim: [The aim of the training is actually the learning goal, which is long-term and broad. It lay out the general goal for the training or course, and it may not be measurable.]

Learning objectives: [There are several ways to formulate course objectives. By formulating objectives, you can make clear what you want learners to achieve during the course. You can formulate task objectives, course objectives and final qualifications. Learning objectives are statements that describe what information, skills, and behaviours learners should be able to demonstrate after receiving training. You can start with: “By the end of the course, trainees should be able to” and continue always with actionable verbs (Bloom, B.S., 1956)].

D. Course plan

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom’s verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS <i>[Detail the syllabus, chapters, subchapters and topics in such a manner to obtain the envisaged educational effects]</i>	COGNITIVE AREA <i>[Detail the educational effects as per Bloom’s taxonomy. Refer to objectives and competencies. Explain how the trainees will experience them. Please consider Merrill’s principles.]</i>	TEACHING METHOD <i>[Explain the teaching methods that you chose in order to obtain the educational effects. Refer to 5E and Merrill’s principles from the perspective of the trainer. Explain what the actions of the teacher will be to obtain the results.]</i>
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES <i>[To ensure you are improving knowledge transfer, you need to help trainees to practice new skills]</i>	PRACTICAL AREA <i>[Detail the educational objectives.]</i>	TEACHING METHODS <i>[Explain the teaching methods that you chose to facilitate the practice.]</i>
	DAILY EVALUATION <i>[To be able to support trainees and to improve the course, it is recommended to monitor and evaluate the progress.]</i>	TASKS FOR TRAINEES <i>[Trainees tasks here]</i>	TEACHING METHODS <i>[Teaching methods here]</i>

E. Explanation of the assessment system

[While most prefer multiple-choice questions, for those who want to test and improve understanding, analytical skills and the ability to synthesize and create new things, the MCQ assessment could be problematic. You can choose observation, peer feedback, projects or essays.]

F. References:

[This section emphasizes the studies, books and educational links necessary to implement the program.]

Access and Inclusion

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

The course “Access and inclusion” deals with the competences necessary for overcoming different forms of the digital divide and opening digital spaces to minorities and different opinions. Online environments are ideal spaces for expanding multiculturalism and democratic values. When abused, this can result in the opposite effects. This course intends to teach participants how to guide themselves and others into more open attitudes and inclusive behaviours to embrace the diversity inherent in the online community and resolve conflicts by expressing themselves in more productive ways while guarding against unproductive divisive attitudes.

Course structure

The course is structured into five modules

- Module 1: Introduction to the concept of Access and Inclusion
- Module 2: Are we all Prejudiced?
- Module 3: Democracy and the Digital
- Module 4: Trolls and other creatures of the net
- Module 5: Become an Access & Inclusion champion

Essential questions

Trainees will remember the many digital concepts and terms associated with access and inclusion in the short term, how prejudice works and why it is a barrier to access and inclusion in the medium term and why access and inclusion are important to democracy in the long run.

Students can address real-life situations by being better able to recognize unacceptable behaviours that discriminate against themselves or other users while being afforded the knowhow to address this and become more effective while performing related daily tasks more efficiently by learning how to steer clear from time-consuming users

Students will learn that access and inclusion in the digital world are fundamental for today's Real-world. They will become champions of access and inclusion while making them better-informed citizens.

Using the knowledge obtained from this course, trainees will learn how to better contextualize online content assigning it the gravity it deserves and promote access and inclusion as a universal right

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	Digital concepts and terms associated with access and inclusion in the short term, how prejudice works and why it is a barrier to access and inclusion in the medium term and why access and inclusion are important to democracy in the long run
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	Students can address real-life situations by being better able to recognize unacceptable behaviours that discriminate against themselves or other users while being afforded the knowhow to address this and become more effective while performing

	related daily tasks more efficiently by learning how to steer clear from time-consuming users.
What should trainees understand about the topic?	Students will learn that access and inclusion in the digital world are fundamental in today's digital world, to become better-informed citizens.
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	Using the knowledge obtained from this course, trainees will learn how to better contextualize online content assigning it the gravity it deserves and promote access and inclusion as a universal right

B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

Learner-centred pedagogy.

- Students use prior knowledge and new experiences to develop new skills (constructivism)
- Teachers create the educational context and facilitate the learning process, guiding students as they learn new concepts
- Reflective approach. Teacher is observer
- Integrative approach. Real-world application

The lesson mixes a general theoretical background with Real-worlds case studies. Infographics are used and videos while an overall assessment takes place on the overall delivery of each module accompanied by a short quiz to be completed online by learners. All participants will have access to educational materials, tools and resources. All learners will gain a badge after the successful completion of the activities for the course and be eligible for the second module. Completion of all modules will earn them the necessary stars to acquire a certificate on the lesson. Trainees gain badges and are granted access to the next module.

Course introduction

The course starts with a video presentation to introduce the course, by the trainer. Alternatively, a short quiz will be introduced to activate the trainees' interest and to help them assess and think about their own practices related to their health and wellbeing when using digital means and technologies.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize hierarchical structures and illustrate relationships among various components of the educational material
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).
- The course documentation is written in EN/RO/DE/GR.

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

Upon successful completion of this course, the participants are expected to be able to:

- Recognize the importance of access and inclusion

- Identify discriminatory behaviours
- Understand how interlinked access and inclusion is with democracy
- Identify personal prejudice and bias
- Employ methods to combat own prejudice and bias
- Understand the differences between real and fake stories
- Recognize the relation between digital democracy and physical democracy
- Encourage and promote positive online behaviours and inclusiveness

Competencies developed through the course:

- Capacity to understand the importance of access and inclusion
- Ability to champion access and inclusion
- Ability to protect oneself and others from discriminatory behaviours
- Ability to use major online applications safely
- Ability to interact with social media in an inclusive and democratic manner
- An attitude that promotes positive online behaviours and interactions with respect to digital democracy

The course is made of five modules. The first two begin by introducing learners to the concepts and gradually build up by demonstrating the usefulness of the skills to be learned, the next two involve the connection of these skills with Democracy and how to recognize patterns of behaviour while the fifth module binds them all together transforming participant into champions of Access and Inclusion. All the course is drafted in the same light to effect consistency and involve a small case study that is gradually applied in a forum conversation to a greater extend.

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Module 1: Introducing the concepts of Access and Inclusion</p> <p>Introduction with key terms</p> <p>Topic 1 What is Access?</p> <p>Topic 2 What is Inclusion?</p> <p>Topic 3 Why is Access and Inclusion Important</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>BLOOMS TAXONOMY</p> <p>Remember An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take always including basic e presence concept and evolution</p> <p>Understand The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will actively engage in forum discussions and take questions while making clarifications between</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to complement a lively forum discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by inviting learners to write down personal examples offering and inviting different views for</p>

		<p>situations and concepts such what is access hindrance and access constrains</p> <p>Apply Trainees will be invited to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation such as with the use of their favourite social media</p> <p>Analyse Trainees will be invited to compare, contrast and differentiate between the real-world examples provided and their personal situation</p> <p>Evaluate Trainees will be asked to support and defend a course of action and responses given to imaginary scenarios on the forum.</p> <p>Create Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions. They will note the key differences between access and inclusion and how the two relate</p> <p>SKILLS</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the fictional and real examples provided.</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner through the showcasing of writing down how they plan to react to new situation comparing how they reacted to the past.</p>	<p>themselves while trainer gives own personal example on access and inclusion, they experienced for both situations they were denied and granted</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through relatable Real-world and fictional examples provided explain how access and inclusion can have very real effects</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner by inviting learners to examine the examples they provided having written them down and how they would have reacted differently using their new knowledge</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to demonstrate how and if there was a change of attitude in the approach, they take on their self-evaluation form</p>
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		<p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the explaining by the learners of the key takeaways they value more and belief will affect their reaction in the future on the self-assessment.</p>	
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA</p> <p>Actively participates in exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Forum, discussion, reflection, solo exercise, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, what if analysis, open on-line dialogue</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz at home</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary quiz</p>
Module 2	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Module 2: Are we all Prejudiced? Introduction with key terms Topic 1: How our mind works Topic 2: How to combat Prejudice</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>BLOOMS TAXONOMY</p> <p>Remember An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take always Understand</p>	<p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for</p>

		<p>The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will participate in forum discussions and take questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts such as prejudice and discrimination</p> <p>Apply Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation through self-evaluation and writing down of personal relatable examples</p> <p>Analyse Trainees will be invited to compare, contrast and differentiate between the real-world examples provided and their personal situations as well as that of their peers through on-line forum discussions.</p> <p>Create Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions.</p> <p>SKILLS Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems through the real-world examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved.</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner</p>	<p>new knowledge and skill by inviting learners to recollect on personal examples offering and inviting conflicting views and attempting to merge them together while trainer gives own personal example on prejudicial instances</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through relatable Real-world and fictional examples provided explaining how prejudice can have very real effects</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner by inviting learners to examine the example provided and they would have reacted differently using their new knowledge</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to demonstrate how and if there was a change of attitude in their approach, they take on online behaviour</p>
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	<p>through the fictional examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved.</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner through the showcasing of how they plan to react to new situation comparing how they reacted to the past.</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the explaining by the learners of the key takeaways they value more and belief will affect their reaction in the future through the self-evaluation.</p>	
<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA Actively participates in exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS Guided online discussion, reflection, solo exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, open dialogue</p>
<p>DAILY EVALUATION Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz</p>	<p>Tasks for Trainees Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz at home</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p>

	quiz		Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary
Module 3	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Module 3: Democracy and the Digital</p> <p>Introduction with key terms</p> <p>Topic 1</p> <p>How democracy works</p> <p>Topic 2:</p> <p>How the digital makes democracy better</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>BLOOMS TAXONOMY</p> <p>Remember</p> <p>An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts</p> <p>Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take away. A small summary of the previous two modules will be given</p> <p>Understand</p> <p>The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will take on-line questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts. The course will also explain how democracy works in the online world</p> <p>Apply</p> <p>Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation.</p> <p>Analyse</p> <p>Trainees will be asked to compare, contrast and differentiate between the real-world examples provided and their personal situation as well as that of their peers through the online forum.</p> <p>Create</p> <p>Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions through a self-assessment.</p> <p>SKILLS</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by inviting learners to write down personal examples offering and inviting conflicting views</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through relatable Real-world and fictional examples provided explaining how online democracy can have very real effects on e-presence and the physical world</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner by inviting learners to examine the examples provided and how they would have reacted differently</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to demonstrate how and if there was a change of attitude in the approach, they take on</p>

		<p>Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems through the real-world examples provided above contrasting different opinions online on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill through the personal examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved by applying on themselves to better comprehend past personal occurrences</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the fictional examples provided above contrasting online different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner through the showcasing of how they plan to react to new situation comparing how they reacted to the past with the use of the self-assessment</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the explaining by the learners of the key takeaways they value more and belief will affect their reaction in the future through the online quiz</p>	<p>matters of inclusion and online democracy</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Real-world Example analysis</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p>

	<p>Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis</p> <p>PRACTICAL AREA Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA Actively participates in exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance</p>	<p>Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA Actively participates in class exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance</p>	<p>Guided online discussion, reflection, solo exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, what if analysis, open dialogue</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz at home</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary applied learning exercise</p>
Module 4	<p>Module 4: Trolls and other creatures of the net Introduction with key terms Topic 1: Unacceptable behaviours, From Bulling to Fake News Topic 2: What you should know about the dangers of the Digital world</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA BLOOMS TAXONOMY</p> <p>Remember An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take aways.</p> <p>Understand The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will take questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts.</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by using the learner's own</p>

		<p>Apply Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation.</p> <p>Analyse Trainees will be asked to compare, contrast and differentiate between the best practice examples provided and their personal situation as well as that of their peers.</p> <p>Evaluate Trainees will be asked to support and defend a course of action and responses given to imaginary scenarios as well as the contrast provided between the different situation described such as with the real-world examples provided.</p> <p>SKILLS Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems by learning how to protect themselves and others</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill through the best practice's examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the personal examples provided</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world</p>	<p>exposure to the concepts</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the use of trainers' own experience and case study presented</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to express what has changed in their approach through the self-assessment and quiz</p>
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		through the self-assessment and quiz	
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis preparing learner for future situations</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA</p> <p>Actively participates in exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Guided discussion, reflection, solo exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, what if analysis, open dialogue</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz at home</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <p>Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary quiz</p>
Module 5	<p>Module 5: Become an Access and Inclusion champion Introduction with key terms Topic 1: Be the Change Topic 2: How to stay safe and protect others Topic 3: A brave new World</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>BLOOMS TAXONOMY Remember An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take away.</p> <p>Understand The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will take questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts</p> <p>Apply</p>	<p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by inviting learners to give personal examples and reconsidering how safe their behaviour was</p>

	<p>Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation reflecting on behaviour they now view as digitally wrong</p> <p>Evaluate Trainees will be asked to note down measures they will adopt to improve the world around them</p> <p>Create Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions.</p> <p>SKILLS Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems by demonstrating how they can become champions of digital democracy</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill through the review of their personal choices in effecting positive change in their surroundings</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the personal examples of change the trainer gives</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the explaining by the learners of the key takeaways they value more and belief will affect their reaction in the future and course taken</p>	<p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through relatable Real-world and fictional examples provided explain how learners can become champions of the concepts</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner by indicating learners to write down personal changes they intend to make</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to demonstrate if there was a change of attitude in the approach, they take</p>	
PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis	PRACTICAL AREA		TEACHING METHODS Guided discussion, reflection, solo

	Fictional Example Analysis Safeguards in plan	Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations EDUCATIONAL AREA Actively participates in exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance	exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, what if analysis, open dialogue
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz quiz	DAILY EVALUATION Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz	TEACHING METHOD Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary

E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks. Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all five modules and gain all five badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

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Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Learning and Creativity

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

If it is no longer possible to learn at school all the knowledge you will need for the rest of your life, then how you learn becomes more important than what you learn, even more so when you consider the rapid evolutions digital technology is bringing to the way we live. It has modified both the tools and platforms that support learning and knowledge access, replacing the traditional chalk and talk mode of knowledge transmission with interactive information and communication tools including and combining websites, e-mail exchanges, chat rooms, video conferencing, webinars, apps, robots, drones, virtual reality and more. eBooks, and the encyclopaedia by Wikipedia and the like are replacing printed books.

Learning and creativity refer to the willingness and the attitude of citizens towards learning in digital environments over their life course, both to develop and express different forms of creativity, with different tools, in different contexts. From this perspective, this course covers the development of personal and professional competences as citizens prepare for the challenges of technology-rich societies with confidence and in innovative ways.

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and five tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own peace. The five modules are:

- Module 1: Education, learning and citizenship
- Module 2: Reflection
- Module 3: Creativity
- Module 4: Putting creativity into practice
- Module 5: Media

Essential questions

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	<p>In days / Weeks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ On short term, we expect the trainees to express different forms of creativity, with different tools, in different contexts. <p>Months</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ On medium term, it is expected to manifest an increased willingness and a positive attitude towards learning in digital environments
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<p>Real-life situations / Daily tasks / Regular activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ During their regular activities, trainees will apply creativity and will think out of the box, which is an important component of problem-solving
What should trainees understand about the topic?	Importance and necessity

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is important for trainee to understand that the way that they learn becomes more important than what they actually know and learn.
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge and Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competency to develop effective learning strategy through reflection Competency to use metaphors in addressing various situations Skills to use strategies for solving out of the box problems Ability to create an environment favourable for creativity

B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

The training is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises and questionnaires. Tasks to measure students' progress and the level of understanding are gradually introduced throughout the course. During the online course, each participant will have access to a set of educational materials. After successfully solving the tasks, the trainees gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

Course introduction

The course starts with a video presentation to introduce the course and a forum question addressed by course coordinator to help the students become familiar with peers and with the topics of the course.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize hierarchical structures and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational material
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

Upon successful completion of this course, the participants will have the ability to express creativity and take on a more active role in the learning process encourages engagement and participation, two essential building blocks in citizenship.

- Characterize the learning process;
- Describe learners' characteristics;
- Justify the importance of education.

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS	COGNITIVE AREA	TEACHING METHODS

Module 1	Education, learning and citizenship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General education and types of education - A world without education - Learner's attributes - Learning from failure 	ABILITIES Upon completing this module, you will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Characterize the learning process; ■ Describe learners' characteristics; ■ Justify the importance of education. 	Discussions Presentation
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Case study - J.K. Rowling - The author of Harry Potter "The secret of life is to fall seven times and to get up eight times." Paulo Coelho	PRACTICAL AREA Guiding questions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What can I learn from this? 2. What could I have done differently? 3. Do I need to acquire or improve some skills? 4. Whom can I learn from? 5. What will I do next? 	PRACTICAL AREA Discussions Analyse Real-world examples Debriefing
	DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. Do you sometimes wish that schools would disappear? How do you think it would affect society?	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Analyse the impact of schools on society; Express the opinion about society.	TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection
Module 2	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Reflection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - About reflection - Why to reflect - Elements of the reflective process - What does reflection involve - Reflective writing - Reflective questions - Nine questions to improve your thinking - Learners' traits and performance 	COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES Upon completing this module, you will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Describe the reflective process; ■ Develop effective learning strategy through reflection; ■ Organize your thoughts in a reflective way. 	TEACHING METHODS Discussions Presentation
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Exercise: A reflective experience	PRACTICAL AREA Express the thoughts in a reflective way; Write about a personal experience;	PRACTICAL AREA Discussions Reflective writing Debriefing

		Express a future perspective about the personal experience	
	DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. Were you doing reflections before? How were you doing it and in what kind of moments?	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Recognize the presence of the reflective process in your life; Describe your way of reflecting	TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection
Module 3	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Creativity</p> <p>How does the internet promote creativity What is creativity Four categories of creativity</p> <p>Creativity myths and misconceptions</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES</p> <p>Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Define the concept of creativity; ■ Give examples of creativity outputs; ■ Explain the 4 C model of creativity. 	TEACHING METHODS Discussions Presentation
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Exercise: Two buckets	PRACTICAL AREA Create a new product for a company; Describe the new product	PRACTICAL AREA Presentation Brainstorming Debriefing
	DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. Tell us about an example of creativity in your everyday life that you experience and describe why it represents creativity for you	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Define creativity; Give examples of daily creativity	TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection
Module 4	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Creativity into practice</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5 steps to optimize your brain for discoveries - A 4-step evolutionary creative process - Using combinatorial creativity - Skills you need to express your creativity - Metaphors to inspire creative thinking - Thinking outside the box 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES</p> <p>Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Enumerate strategies for creativity; ■ Solve think out of the box problems; ■ Explain metaphors 	TEACHING METHODS Discussions Presentation

	<p style="text-align: center;">T H I N K O U T S I D E T H E B O X</p>		
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Exercise: How creative are you</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Identify the personal level of creativeness Do the test to determine if you have the personality traits, attitudes, values, motivations, and interests that characterize creativity</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Discussions Testing Debriefing</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. How does the 4-step evolutionary creative process apply to small and large creative acts?</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES Use this 4-step model to describe how you post something on social media (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Snapchat etc.) Apply the 4-step evolutionary creative process on social media</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection</p>
<p>Module 5</p>	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A short brief about environments - Innovative environment - Creative environment - How to make a creative environment at school - Social media environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community service: service learning - Examples of service learning and community service activities 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Describe different types of environments; ■ Create an environment favourable for creativity; ■ Identify types of service learning. 	<p>TEACHING METHODS Discussions Presentation</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES CASE STUDY: What? So what? Now what?</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Reflect on a given situation. Interpret a given role. Describe a given situation from a personal perspective</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Discussions Reflect on the case study Resume the reflection</p>

			Debriefing
	DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. Do you consider that schools are a creative environment? Why yes? Why not?	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Express personal opinion about creativity in schools; Argue personal opinion about creativity in schools	TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection

E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks. Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all five modules and gain all five badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

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GR: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Learning-and-Creativity-GR.pdf>

Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Media and Information Literacy

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

Often, we talk about human rights like access to information, to education, free expression or social life participation. Many young people fight for them, which is very good. Surprisingly, once youth have them, they do not exactly understand how to use those rights. The way they use them is very much dependent on whether young people are literate enough to attain them. The media literacy level give youth the degree of independency in using their rights. This model course is an instrument for teachers to evaluate the level of youth literacy and to help them exceed the media and information literacy baseline. The proposed exercises are developed to improve the medial and information literacy skills of youth while raising their willing to correctly take advantages of own rights.

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and five tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own peace. The MIL course is available online and participants can join anytime.

Essential questions

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do in days, weeks, months from now?	<p>In days / Weeks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Know how to fully understand found information, or know where to go for help if needed to understand it <p>Months</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept: MIL implies having <i>access</i> to the media and information, <i>understanding</i> the media and information and <i>creating/expressing</i> oneself using the media and information
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<p>Real-life situations / Daily tasks / Regular activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Know how to organize, analyse, interpret and evaluate information, including source reliability Know how to communicate and present the information to others in appropriate and usable formats and mediums.
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<p>Importance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MIL like a habit: ability to use functions of equipment, competence of navigation through menu, competence to control media <p>Necessity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Know how to utilize the information to solve a problem, make a decision or meet a need
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge and Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Realize that if a need or problem exists, it requires information

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Know how to accurately identify and define the information needed to meet the need, solve the problem, or make the decision ■ Know how to create, or to facilitate creation of, unavailable information that you need;
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B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

The training is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by infographics, practical exercises and questionnaires. Tasks to measure students' progress and the level of understanding are gradually introduced throughout the course. During the online course, each participant will have access to a set of educational materials. After successfully solving the tasks, the trainees gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

Course introduction

The course starts with a video presentation to introduce the course, by the trainer. Alternatively, a short quiz will be introduced to activate the trainees' interest and to help them assess and think on their own practices related to their health and wellbeing when using digital means and technologies.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize hierarchical structures and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational material
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).
- The course documentation is written in EN/RO/DE/GR.

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

The old cliché, 'make people work smarter, not just harder,' it is more actual than ever. It defines how the MIL impact the workforce of the 21st century. People are now able to become independent learners and critical thinkers. The better will integrate MIL skills in their daily routine, the more independent and efficient they would be.

Media and information literacy course aims to equip youth with critical information skills, which are crucial for your life-long learning. Participants in this course will identify the effects that media and advertising have on us; understand benefits and potential negative effects of media content and the importance of real-world knowledge.

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Introduction to Media and Information Literacy a. Media Literacy	Understanding the Role of Media and Information in Democracy The learner should be able to:	Content related to real-life situation. Problem-Centred – present a real-life

	b. Information Literacy c. Technology Literacy	- define information needs - explain the role and functions of media in democratic societies - describe how communication is affected by media and information	situation to engaged in solving problems Learner-centred pedagogy. - Students use prior knowledge and new experiences to develop new skills
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Class activity – Share your media habits, lifestyles and preferences to your classmates (face to face or online via forum)	Task: - describe a responsible use of media - structure the content and ideas - give feedback Poster analysis A task card titled 'Poster Analysis' with a portrait of Abraham Lincoln. It contains two questions: 'What is the message of this poster?' and 'Do you agree with the message? Why or why not?'. A quote from Lincoln is also present: 'Don't believe everything you read on the internet just because there's a picture with a quote next to it.' - Abraham Lincoln	1 st Engage of 5E Ask trainees to describe/ write down what they already know about the topic
	EVALUATION Forum posts and reply	Task for trainees: Know-Want-Learned chart – exercise	Forum
Module 2	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Types of Media a. Print (books, newsletter, magazines, journals, and other printed materials) b. Broadcast (radio, television, and film) c. New Media (internet) Media and Information Sources a. Indigenous b. Library c. Internet d. Others/ Mass Media Pros and Cons of Different Types of Media - as sources of information	Understanding Media Content and Its Uses The learner should be able to: - identify sources of information - determine the accuracy of content A. Matching Type. Choose the letter of the answer that is related to the given concept. Answer may be repeated. 1. Television a. Print Media 2. Book b. Broadcast Media 3. Internet c. New media 4. Blog 5. Film	Demonstration principle of instruction. Demonstrate the information via specific situations or cases (multiple examples).
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Q1. What makes a particular media platform appealing and useful?	Task: - compare potential sources of media and information - evaluate the use of different type of media	2 nd Explore of 5E Explore new concepts, review materials/ videos/ photos or articles and make observations.

	Why do young people prefer to use the internet to traditional media?		Discuss with peers.
	DAILY EVALUATION 5-Question Quiz	Task for trainees: - Solve questionnaire, Matching questions	Moodle quiz
Module 3	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Legal, Ethical, and Societal Issues in Media and Information a. Copyright/Fair Use/Plagiarism b. Netiquette c. Digital Divide, Addiction, and Bullying d. Virtual Self e. Others	Accessing Information Effectively and Efficiently Applying New and Traditional Media Formats The learner should be able to: - apply retrieval tools - put into practice the understanding of the intellectual property	3 rd Explain of 5E Relate the content to the previous module Use video, software Application – recognize divergent examples
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Exercise to promote ethical use of media	Task: - discuss issues related to copyright 	Present and discuss: an interview with a celebrity in a role-playing scenario (well-known)
	DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply	Task for trainees: - Enumerate opportunities and challenges in media and information	Moodle forum
Module 4	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Media and Information Literate Individual a. Improved quality of life b. Greater political participation c. Better economic opportunities d. Improved learning environment e. More cohesive social units f. Others	Situating the Sociocultural Context of Media Content The learner should be able to: - product media and information content - comprehend how manipulative information and media are formally and informally produced, organized, and disseminated	4 th Elaborate of 5 E Present tutorials: how to create a webpage, undertake a video production, do a broadcast morning news program, or act as a reporter Storyboard
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Peer critique activities	Task: - Constructively critically evaluate each other's work.	Integration principle of instruction and Investigation

	DAILY EVALUATION Assessment	Tasks for trainees: - produce and evaluate a creative text/visual/audio-based presentation using design principle and elements	Assignment evaluation, storyboard
Module 5	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Dimensions of media a. Text Information b. Visual Information c. Audio Information Manipulative Information and Media a. Definition, characteristics, format and types, sources, advantages and limitations, and value b. Selection Criteria c. Design principle and Elements	Critically Evaluating Information and Information Source The learner should be able to: - assess information sources against reliability, validity, accuracy, authority, timeliness, and points of view or biases among several evaluation criteria	Inquiry Learning Learning directed by questions, problems, or challenges that student's work to address.
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES CRAAP criteria exercise Accuracy Author Currency Fairness Relevance	Task: - Analyse the infographics with CRAAP criteria 	5 th Evaluate of 5E Observe trainees' skills Application – execute the 5 steps of CRAAP
	DAILY EVALUATION Questionnaire	Task for trainees: Solve quiz	5-MCQ Moodle

E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks.

Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all five modules and gain all five badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

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Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Ethics and Empathy

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

Ethics and Empathy are those behaviours that maintain “peace”! Understanding others’ feelings and reasons is paramount if individuals are to live their online experiences positively. The concept behind “Ethics” is quite old and complex. In Ancient Greece, it used to refer to the set of behaviours that an ideal society took as “good” or “positive” to keep or achieve peace and order. Something defined as “ethical” not only refers to a set of moral behaviours but comprises the whole idea of moving towards what is good and positive and, moreover, caring for others.

This course provides an understanding of the roles of Ethics and Empathy in the digital world. Unethical online behaviours have negative, even dramatic consequences and this course is intended to develop a learning environment that promotes positive behaviours and interactions.

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and five tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own peace. The five modules are:

- Module 1: Positive online behaviour
- Module 2: Empathy as a skill for life
- Module 3: Ethical thinking
- Module 4: Ethical decisions
- Module 5: Practice empathy

Essential questions

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	<p>In days / Weeks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ On short term, we expect the trainees to recognize positive/negative behaviour interactions in the online world. ■ They will be able to make decisions from an ethical standpoint <p>Months</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ On medium term, it is expected to practice empathy and promote positive online behaviours. In addition, we expect them to practice integrity when faced with ethical dilemmas
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<p>Real-life situations / Daily tasks / Regular activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ During their regular activities, trainees will practice and gradually improve their empathy, to understand and feel other people’s experiences, feelings and points of view.
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<p>Importance and necessity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Unethical online behaviours have negative, even dramatic consequences

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is important for trainee to understand that it is about caring and acting to make online environments more positive, productive and meaningful places.
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge and Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competency to create online interactions that promote positive behaviour Ability to recognize and treat negative behaviour online Capacity to illustrate empathic behaviour in online communication Skills to use techniques to correct someone in a professional way Ability to maintain integrity when faced with ethical dilemmas

B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

The training is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises and questionnaires. Tasks to measure students' progress and the level of understanding are gradually introduced throughout the course. During the online course, each participant will have access to a set of educational materials. After successfully solving the tasks, the trainees gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

Course introduction

The course starts with a video presentation to introduce the course and a forum question addressed by course coordinator to help the students become familiar with peers and with the topics of the course.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize hierarchical structures and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational material
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

Upon successful completion of this course, the participants will have the ability to illustrate empathic behaviour in online communication.

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Positive online behaviour</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to use social media in a positive way 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES</p> <p>Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Presentation</p> <p>Examples</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deal with negative online behaviour - Recognize trolls - Professional support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Use social media in a positive way ■ Create online interactions that promote positive behaviour ■ Recognize and deal with negative behaviour online 	
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Exercise: The public meltdown of Amy's Bakery</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Read the case study</p> <p>Reflect on:</p> <p>How are Amy and Samy's interactions with key audiences positive? How are they negative?</p> <p>Do you think the media's response was ethical towards Amy's Baking Company? Why or why not?</p> <p>Do you think Amy's Baking Company's response was ethical towards their online reviewers? Why or why not?</p> <p>How could Amy's Baking Company have built a better relationship with their clientele?</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Reflect on the case study</p> <p>Resume the reflection</p> <p>Debriefing</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Quiz</p> <p>Forum. What are the most appropriate methods to promote positive behaviour</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Identify online interactions that promote positive behaviour</p> <p>Structure the content and ideas</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Assessment test</p> <p>Forum discussion</p> <p>Self-reflection</p>
Module 2	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Empathy as a skill for life</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Empathy – a necessary skill - Categories of empathy - Pro and Cons Stories - Empathy during online communication 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>ABILITIES</p> <p>Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Understand the importance of empathy ■ Explain what it means to have different perspectives on empathy ■ Illustrate emphatic behaviour in online communication 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Presentation</p> <p>Stories</p> <p>Case studies</p> <p>Reflect on the case study</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Exercise: Empathy Quiz The quiz contains 28 questions. The first 22 will be used to measure your level of empathy; the last six are included to understand how</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Do the test!</p> <p>Reflect of results!</p> <p>Would you like to change something? What would be the steps?</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Questionnaire, score and feedback</p> <p>Debriefing</p>

	empathy relates to factors like gender, birth order, and political orientation		
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Quiz</p> <p>Forum. The teacher responded to one student "I know exactly how you feel. Let me tell you what I do in those situations."</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Read the situation</p> <p>Answer the questions: What would have been your reaction if you were the teacher?</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Assessment test</p> <p>Forum discussion</p> <p>Self-reflection</p>
Module 3	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Ethical thinking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethical online behaviour - Take care of self-image - Relationship and communication. Ethical discourse online - Ethical thinking - Case study: Your colleague is wrong. How to act? <p>90% of employers say social media is important when evaluating a job candidate.</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>ABILITIES</p> <p>Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Understand ethical behaviour ■ Explain how the use of social media can affect your future ■ Correct somebody in a professional way 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Presentation</p> <p>Reflect on the case study</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Exercise: Check the politeness with online instruments</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Write a message to ask for support!</p> <p>Tasks: Prepare your request. Write a few sentences to make someone understand what you need. Then, copy/paste in the online instrument</p> <p>http://politeness.cornell.edu/</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Creative text elaboration</p> <p>Online checking</p> <p>Review and Analyse</p> <p>Reflect on the results</p> <p>Debriefing</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Quiz</p> <p>Forum. Understand the willingness of non-native digital individuals to talk in-</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Read about digital immigrants</p> <p>Share your understanding of the digital immigrants</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Assessment test</p> <p>Forum discussion</p> <p>Self-reflection</p>

	person or on the phone, rather than via chat.		
Module 4	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Ethical decisions Dealing with ethical dilemmas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be a responsible digital citizen - Five reasons for using social media 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Practice integrity when faced with ethical dilemmas ■ Explain your personal responsibility to others on social media 	<p>TEACHING METHODS Discussions Presentation</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Exercise: Spot the troll</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Read the messages written on social media by trolls or/ genuine and identify if you are facing a troll. The test is available online here: https://spotthetroll.org/</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Discussions Reflect on the case study Resume the reflection Debriefing</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. How can we improve our skills to detect trolls?</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES Evaluate your abilities to spot the troll Respond to the forum question</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection</p>
Module 5	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Practice empathy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Keep balance - Practice empathy - Dos and don'ts - Professional support. Use Web App that Facilitates Better Online Conversations 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Understand and feel other people's experiences, feelings and points of view ■ Create online interactions that promote positive online behaviours ■ Evaluate peers online interactions from an ethical and empathic perspective 	<p>TEACHING METHODS Discussions Presentation Testing Reflection</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Test: Check your online conversation Use online tools the check http://faciloscope.cal.msu.edu/facilitation/</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Write 3-4 lines to introduce an idea, connect with other ideas that may be already posted, share from your experience</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Discussions Reflect on the comments Resume the reflection Debriefing</p>

		and/or invite others to share from their practices. Copy/paste the text in the App Check the App comments How this new kind of comment analysis technology can help?	
	DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. Social media posts or other comments foster engagement	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Express personal opinion about online trolls Argue personal opinion about online trolls	TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection

E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks.

Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all five modules and gain all five badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion...

F. REFERENCES:

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<https://www.buzzfeednews.com/article/ryanhatesthis/digiorno-whyistayed-you-had-pizza>

<https://www.searchenginejournal.com/learned-15-epic-social-media-fails/121432/>

<https://www.techrepublic.com/article/virtual-meeting-101-body-language-tips-for-zoom-teams-and-life/>

<http://politeness.cornell.edu/>

<https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20200930-can-empathy-be-bad-for-you>

Textbooks:

EN: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Ethics-and-Empathy.pdf>

RO: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Ethics-and-Empathy-RO.pdf>

GE: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Ethics-and-Empathy-DE.pdf>

GR: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Ethics-and-Empathy-GR.pdf>

Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Health and Wellbeing

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

This course addresses two elements of digital citizenship: the physical (health) and psychological wellbeing (wellness) of one's self while living and interacting in an ever-increasing digital technological world. Given the high frequency with which young people use technologies, particularly in their personal lives, health and wellbeing are areas that need to be addressed in the interest of developing well-balanced future citizens.

In the physical health aspect, the ergonomics of the workstation have become more important than ever, given the frequency and duration of use of technologies. Some injuries that can be avoided include repetitive stress injuries, eye strain and carpal tunnel syndrome. Simple solutions such as table height or screen placement can preclude health problems. In the psychosocial aspect, it is recognized that a cultural shift is occurring with respect to what is expected of individuals in social settings, in relationships with others through and with technology (e.g. social media, online forums, etc.). The nature of highly mobile and highly connected technology places pressure on the nature of social connectedness and behaviour, both physical and virtual. Among the most alarming facts related to youth's health and wellbeing is the rising percentages of young people suffering from some type of media addiction. They exhibit compulsive behaviour that interferes with their normal living and causes high levels of stress on family, friends and one's work environment (Young, 2009). Achieving balance has become a very relevant characteristic of healthy citizens.

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and five tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own pace. The Health and Wellbeing course is available online and participants can join anytime.

Essential questions

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	<p>In 4 days:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To remember the information presented in the course and the ways they can achieve health and wellbeing in their daily online practices. ■ To gain the essential knowledge on how their wellbeing is endangered by the potential use, misuse and overuse of the digital and technological media devices <p>In Weeks/ Months:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To be able to understand and assess their own practices when using digital media and technologies and change them accordingly, in order to achieve health and wellbeing ■ To remember and apply useful tips on their personal use of media and computers (e.g. Related to ergonomics, sleep, social interactions and personal relationships)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To know the criteria based on which a behaviour related to the use of digital means can be considered as addiction, and the ways to address this addiction ■ To learn how to moderate their use of digital means for their own benefit and for the benefit of their work, family, and social environment ■ To know how to address issues related to digital health and wellbeing when interacting with others
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<p>Beyond the classroom:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Know how to assess their online behaviours and practices and how to amend them for their own benefit ■ Know where to turn in case they feel addicted to the internet and the media ■ Know and apply good and healthy digital behaviours and avoid negative and dangerous ones ■ Realize the extent to which their use of digital means and technologies can affect their body and mind ■ Know how to keep the balance between the online and offline worlds
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The importance of assessing and adjusting practices and behaviours related to digital means in order to maintain a good physical and psycho-social state ■ The necessity of balancing online and offline activities for their wellbeing ■ The connection and interdependence of the online and offline world and their effect on people's physical and psycho-social health ■ The connection of the digital health and wellbeing to their roles as active citizens in their societies
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge: Trainees will know:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The specific key digital health issues which arise from non-ergonomically friendly practices ■ Specific safe and dangerous online practices ■ The means to maintain their physical health despite the extensive use of digital devices ■ The key digital wellness issues which arise from overusing technology and why they occur ■ The ways to avoid psycho-social problems related to the use of media and technology ■ How to identify media and internet addictions and where professional help can be found <p>Skills: Trainees will develop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Self-assessment skills ■ Critical thinking ■ Creativity

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Practices related to the application of theoretical knowledge into practice■ Social skills (for both online and offline environments)
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B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

The training is a combination of a theoretical section and practical activities accompanied by infographics, exercises and questionnaires. Tasks to measure students' progress and the development of the relevant skills and knowledge are gradually introduced throughout the course. During the online course, each participant will have access to a set of educational materials (such as articles, videos and relevant web pages). After successfully solving the tasks, the trainees gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

Course introduction

1.5-2 min video presentation to introduce the course, by the trainer. Alternatively, a short quiz will be introduced to activate the trainees' interest and to help them assess and think on their own practices related to their health and wellbeing when using digital means and technologies.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize learning and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational materials
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).
- The course documentation is written in EN/ RO/DE/GR.

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the course is for trainees to understand the importance of digital health and wellbeing and know the ways to maintain them, in this rapidly evolving digital era. The specific objectives are:

- Trainees will understand what specific key digital health issues arise from non-ergonomically friendly practices
- Trainees will be able to explain and show how specific non-ergonomically friendly practices produce specific health issues
- Trainees will be able to identify specific proven ergonomically solutions to put into place that offset these key digital health issues and why they work
- Trainees will realise the key digital wellness issues which arise from overusing technology and why they occur
- Trainees will understand and apply specific strategies in order to prevent key digital wellness issues
- Trainees will gain deep understanding of different types of media addictions (such as addictions to online games, to social media, FOMO, etc.) and where professional help can be found

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Introduction to digital health and wellbeing.</p> <p>Basic concepts to be introduced in this module are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - physical health - psycho- social health and wellbeing - ergonomics - digital habits - use/ overuse of and addiction to media - The basic elements affecting health and wellbeing (such as posture, time spent on online activities, sleeping habits, etc.). 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identify the means to check their own digital habits - define the basic concepts related to digital health - give examples of good and dangerous digital habits - relate digital habits to health problems <p>SKILLS</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognise their own digital habits - critically think their online behaviours - compare and evaluate different digital habits and conclude on the optimal ones 	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life problems, habits and behaviours to guide students to acquire knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. The questions can be asked after the self-check quiz to promote dialogue and exchange of prior experiences in order to develop new skills
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Class activity: trainees take up the following test: https://plato.algonquincollege.com/ac-library/healthWellness/story.html5.html . It is a self- check quiz, which reveals the extent to which their digital habits affect their well-being. The quiz includes 18 questions, each of which has 4 options. After completing the quiz, trainees share the results with the class and comment on the findings (face to face or online via forum).</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize and describe healthy and unhealthy digital habits - structure the content and ideas - criticize specific digital practices - propose ways to achieve digital health and wellbeing - discuss the effect of specific digital habits on the physical and psycho- social health and well being <p>Analysis of statistical data on the digital habits of young people (country specific/ globally)</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings - presents and comments recent statistical data on the common online behaviours of young people - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions

	DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees: - answer the questions posed at the forum - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting	TEACHING METHODS Forum
Module 2	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Workstation ergonomics During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed: - dangers, injuries, pain and discomfort related to workstation ergonomics - tips and solution of the prevention and elimination of these dangers - creation of the optimal environment to work ergonomically -	KNOWLEDGE Trainees should be able to: - understand how to prevent and eliminate pain, injuries or discomfort when using their computer - realise the aspects which facilitate the creation of an optimal environment for working ergonomically - explain why maintaining and ergonomically safe environment is important for physical health - demonstrate the procedures to keep the workstation environment safe and ergonomically correct SKILLS: Trainees should be able to: - use right posture and movement of the body and limbs as a task is performed - design and use of tools, layout of the work area or equipment ergonomically - to recognize potential physical dangers when using the computer - describe preventive methods of dealing with potential hazards	TEACHING METHOD - The trainer uses real-life situations to demonstrate the concepts and the dangers related to an environment which is not ergonomically correct - The trainer activates trainees' prior knowledge and experience to connect them with the new concepts - The trainer demonstrates the optimal and the dangerous workstation environment - The trainer encourages trainees to apply the new knowledge on their everyday practices related to the use of the computer
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES - Trainees are asked to read this brief article https://www.cnet.com/how-to/wake-up-call-are-you-	Tasks for trainees: - read and contemplate on the usual mistakes people make when using their computers/ mobile devices	TEACHING METHODS The trainer: - uses a PowerPoint presentation on the dangers and the

	<p>making-these-five-ergonomics-mistakes/ on the five ergonomics mistakes people using the computer usually make and the trainer asks for their personal experience</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trainees are asked to watch the following video https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bLBKUbnLYTs&t=11s&ab_channel=Techquickie related to common health problems when using the computer and the different ergonomic and behaviour solutions - Based on the information presented the trainer asks trainees to specify the ways to make an office desk more ergonomic. Trainees are given the following article https://www.cnet.com/how-to/how-to-set-up-an-ergonomic-workstation/ to verify their ideas and proposals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to share their experiences on the health problems related to a non-ergonomically correct environment - to retrieve information presented in the video, in order to form opinions - to apply their prior and new knowledge on the creation of a more ergonomic workplace - to predict future health problems (eyes, back, neck, etc.) by judging one's workstation <p>Exercise: Trainees are shown specific items of a workstation (e.g. desk, screen, mouse, etc) and are asked to create an ergonomic workstation and to explain and justify their choices</p>	<p>solutions related to ergonomics when using a computer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - initiates and facilitates discussions related to the new topics presented - shows the video on the health problems and their solutions and asks for further ideas - prepares a practical exercise so that students apply their knowledge to create an ergonomic workstation - uses brainstorming on the optimal solutions for the development of a safe workstation
	DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - answer the questions posed at the forum - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting 	TEACHING METHODS Forum
Module 3	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Staying Mentally Healthy with Technology</p> <p>The basic concepts presented during this module are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - what causes the constant checking of electronic devices - the link between constant checking and stress 	<p>KNOWLEDGE</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - realize their own behaviours when using the social media - recognize and identify behaviours which can be considered as problematic in the use of social media - analyse the factors which lead to stress and anxiety in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life situations to demonstrate the concepts and the dangers related to the extensive use of social media - The trainer activates trainees' prior knowledge and experience to connect

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - positive and negative sides of the most popular social media - the effects of social media on mental health (such as anxiety and depression) - the impact of social media on people's relationships - the reasons for a "digital detox" and its benefits 	<p>relation to the use of social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - design an alternative pattern on their use of social media, when they feel that it is necessary - determine the ways to achieve "digital detox" <p>SKILLS: Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interpret the signs which indicate problematic use of social media on themselves and on others - present the problematic behaviours related to social media to others for awareness raising purposes - organise and plan a: digital detox" scheme for themselves and for others - select specific behaviours and reactions when using social media -critically think and judge their own social media behaviours 	<p>them with the new concepts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer demonstrates the correct and incorrect behaviours related to social media - The trainer encourages trainees to apply the new knowledge on their everyday practices related to the use of social media - The trainer presents findings and data and initiates discussions on the connection between social media and mental health - The trainer uses case studies to promote trainees' critical thinking and creativity
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trainees watch the following video https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pgo65s1R6TM&ab_channel=TEDxTalks, which explains why being hooked to our Smartphones, is the most interesting - yet silent - addiction of our times. - Trainees go through the following article https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2016/03/160302121325.htm On how the mobile phone use is linked to depression and anxiety. - Trainees are asked to discuss on social media behaviours which are considered problematic and the reasons behind these behaviours 	<p>Tasks for trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discuss the data from the articles and the video on the connection between social media and mental health - evaluate and contemplate on their own behaviours when using (or avoiding) social media - evaluate the case studies presented by the trainer and think of possible solutions to given problems - discuss in small groups the ways to achieve a healthy relationship with others on social media and the Real-world. - brainstorm the advice they would give somebody on the correct use of social media 	<p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - uses a PowerPoint presentation on the dangers and the solutions related to the use of social media - initiates and facilitates discussions related to the new topics presented - shows the video on the connection between anxiety and social media use - prepares a practical exercise so that students apply their knowledge to change their own behaviours when using and interacting on social media

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trainees brainstorm on the characteristics and aspects of online and offline friendships - Trainees discover the ways to achieve a healthy relationship with their social media. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - uses brainstorming on the optimal solutions for the balanced use of social media - prepares case studies to demonstrate to trainees the mental health problems which can arise from the excessive/ improper use of social media - presents the positive sides of social media interactions to point out the need for a balanced use
	DAILY EVALUATION online quiz to assess the skills and knowledge related to the module	Trainees answer the quiz	Online quiz (multiple-choice questions, fill in the gap questions, questions requiring short answers and descriptions.
Module 4	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Media addictions</p> <p>The basic concepts presented during this module are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the meaning and nature of media addictions - the five types of media addictions (e.g. for cybersex, cyber-relationships, online gambling, online games and online purchases) - the reasons behind these addictions - symptoms and diagnosis of media addictions - ways to address and combat media addictions - links to services providing help and support to addicted people 	<p>KNOWLEDGE</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - define the different types of media addictions - recognize the symptoms of any type of media addiction - discuss the causes of these addictions in relation to youth - compare extensive use and addiction of the digital media - diagnose media addictions on themselves and others - propose individualized measures to minimize such addictions <p>SKILLS:</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - compose the profile of a person suffering from some type of media addiction - examine their own media behaviour against the criteria of addiction - develop strategies to minimize these addictions for them or for others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life situations to demonstrate the dangers related to media addictions - The trainer activates trainees' prior knowledge and experience to connect them with the new concepts - The trainer demonstrates the correct and incorrect behaviours related to the avoidance of media addictions - The trainer encourages trainees to apply the new knowledge on their everyday practices related to the use of media - The trainer presents findings and data and initiates discussions on the connection

		- recommend solutions in cases of media addictions	between media addictions and other mental, emotional or physical health problems - The trainer uses case studies to promote trainees' critical thinking and creativity
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>- Trainees take the short following quiz to find out whether they may be suffering from an addiction to the internet: https://www.psycom.net/internet-addiction-test-quiz</p> <p>- Trainees watch the following video https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=iW5nqfurlPs&ab_channel=BBCNewsnight on media addictions and the difference between extensive use and addiction</p> <p>- Trainees watch Dr. Young's presentation on how to identify warning signs of Internet addiction and what we can do to manage technology in our daily lives. https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=vOSYmLER664&ab_channel=TEDxTalks</p>	<p>Tasks for trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - watch the videos and take the test on media addictions - discuss on the signs which are related to media addictions - find solutions to case studies of young people being addicted to the internet and the media - brainstorm ideas on the alternative activities to avoid or minimize media addictions - critically think of the causes of these addictions 	<p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - uses a PowerPoint presentation on media addictions - initiates and facilitates discussions related to the new topics presented - shows the videos on media addictions - prepares a practical exercise so that students apply their knowledge to change their own behaviours in case they feel they are addicted to the Internet - uses brainstorming on the optimal solutions for the balance use of media and the Internet - prepares case studies to demonstrate to trainees the mental health problems which can arise from media addictions
	DAILY EVALUATION online quiz to assess the skills and knowledge related to the module	Trainees answer the quiz	Online quiz (multiple-choice questions, fill in the gap questions, questions requiring short answers and descriptions).
Module 5	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Issues related to the healthy use of digital tools and online devices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - digital footprints - online sharing - online privacy 	<p>KNOWLEDGE</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognise how different aspects of the use of the media can cause mental and emotional problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life situations to demonstrate the dangers related to online privacy and fake news

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fake news - when social media go wrong <p>These issues will be presented and discussed in relation to their possible effects on health and wellbeing. They will be briefly presented and discussed, since some of them will be deeply analysed in different courses and modules.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - realize the importance of online privacy and digital footprints - explain how fake news can cause distress and anxiety - summarize the factors in the use of media that endanger health and wellbeing <p>SKILLS</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - relate specific online behaviours to mental problems - distinguish between fake and real news - to practice safe online behaviours regarding privacy matters - evaluate incidents related to the appearance of health problems from being online - recommend solutions to address privacy issues and the effects of fake news on themselves and on others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer activates trainees' prior knowledge and experience to connect them with the new concepts - The trainer demonstrates the correct and incorrect behaviours related to balancing online and offline life - The trainer encourages trainees to apply the new knowledge on their everyday practices related to the use of media - The trainer presents findings and data and initiates discussions on the connection between media and mental, emotional or physical health problems - The trainer uses case studies to promote trainees' critical thinking and creativity
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trainees watch the following video on how digital information threatens to ruin people's life when it falls into the wrong hands: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H0I7jQb37bo&ab_channel=NOVAPBSOfficial - Trainees read the following article on what to do when matters of online sharing and privacy create problems: https://zvulony.ca/2012/articles/defamation-articles/top-ten-tips-libeled-internet/ 	<p>Tasks for trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - watch the videos on defamation and online privacy - find solutions to case studies of young people who ignored matters of privacy and digital footprints - critically think of the correct media behaviours to avoid mental health problems 	<p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - uses a PowerPoint presentation on usual problems related to online privacy, digital footprints and fake news - initiates and facilitates discussions related to the new topics presented - shows the videos - prepares a practical exercise so that students apply their knowledge to change their own behaviours - uses brainstorming on the optimal solutions for the

			balance use of media and the Internet by respecting privacy and truth - prepares case studies to demonstrate to trainees the mental health problems which can arise from unthoughtful media behaviours
	DAILY EVALUATION online quiz to assess the skills and knowledge related to the module	Trainees answer the quiz	Online quiz (multiple-choice questions, fill in the gap questions, questions requiring short answers and descriptions.

E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks.

Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all five modules and gain five badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

F. REFERENCES:

<https://tlp-lpa.ca/digital-citizenship/health-and-wellness>

<https://sites.google.com/a/aea11.k12.ia.us/heartland-digital-citizenship/health-wellness>

<https://www.rockyview.ab.ca/21stC/supporting/websafety/digital-citizenship/nine-elements/digital-health-and-wellness>

<https://cpb-ca-c1.wpmucdn.com/learningnetwork.setbc.org/dist/d/592/files/2017/11/Digital-Health-and-Wellness-2bdwptp.pdf>

<https://thewellbeingthesis.org.uk/foundations-for-success/digital-wellbeing-how-to-have-a-healthy-digital-diet/> <https://tlp-lpa.ca/digital-citizenship/health-and-wellness>

Textbooks:

EN: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Health-and-Wellbeing.pdf>

RO: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Health-and-Wellbeing-RO.pdf>

GE: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Health-and-Wellbeing-DE.pdf>

GR: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Health-and-Wellbeing-GR.pdf>

Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

E-Presence and Communications

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

Course description: The course “e-Presence and Communications” deals with competences related to online communication and interaction with others through virtual social spaces. More and more people are spending a greater part of their lives online for many reasons that expand beyond work and entertainment. Maintaining an active on-line presence in turns becomes increasingly important in terms of both work and personal life. Knowing how to communicate and address issues related to one’s virtual profile as well as image is among the top eSkill’s that people, especially young ones should master.

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and five tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own peace. The course is available online and participants can join anytime.

Essential questions

Trainees will remember the Best Practices on e-presence and communication in the short run, how to strategically approach e-presence and communication in the meanwhile and how to be safer and moral in the end. Students can address real-life situations by being better able to respond and communicate their meaning while performing related daily tasks more efficiently utilizing best practices and optimizing regular

That e-presence is inescapable for the most part in the modern era. Just as there are good, manners and standards of behaviour in the physical world so there are in the digital one.

Using the knowledge obtained from this course, trainees will learn How to stay safer online and maximize their e-presence results by optimizing and using communication techniques and strategies.

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do in days, weeks, months from now?	<p>In days / Weeks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Know Best Practices on e-presence and communication in the short run <p>Months</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to strategically approach e-presence and communication in the meanwhile and how to be safer and moral in the long run
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<p>Real-life situations / Daily tasks / Regular activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students can address real-life situations by being better able to respond and communicate their meaning while performing related daily tasks more efficiently utilizing best practices and optimizing regular activities performance.
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<p>Importance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> That e-presence is inescapable for the most part in the modern era. <p>Necessity</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Just as there are good, manners and standards of behaviour in the physical world so there are in the digital one.
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge and Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to stay safer online and maximize their e-presence results by optimizing and using communication techniques and strategies

B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

The training is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by infographics, practical exercises and questionnaires. Tasks to measure students' progress and the level of understanding are gradually introduced throughout the course. During the online course, each participant will have access to a set of educational materials. After successfully solving the tasks, the trainees gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

Learner-centred pedagogy: Students use prior knowledge and new experiences to develop new skills (constructivism). The teacher creates the educational context and facilitate the learning process, guiding students as they learn new concepts.

Course introduction

The course starts with a video presentation to introduce the course, by the trainer. Alternatively, a short quiz will be introduced to activate the trainees' interest and to help them assess and think on their own practices related to their health and wellbeing when using digital means and technologies.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize hierarchical structures and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational material
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).
- The course documentation is written in EN/RO/DE/GR.

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

Upon successful completion of this course, the participants are expected to be able to:

- Recognize positive/negative behaviour interactions in online world.
- Identify the trustworthiness of the resources
- Understand how interlinked the online community is and whatever is posted can reaper in numerous forums
- Identify best practices for maintaining a safe and healthy online presence
- Employ e-presence strategies that increase visibility of profile
- Understand the differences between communications in the physical world and the digital world
- Recognize online communication methods and the forms they take
- Create online interactions that promote positive online behaviours

Competencies:

- Capacity to understand online communications
- Ability to communicate online in a proper manner
- Ability to create and sustain an online presence
- Ability to use major online applications
- Ability to interact with social media
- Attitude that promotes positive online behaviours and interactions

The course is made of five modules. The first two begin by introducing learned into the concepts and gradually build up by demonstrating the usefulness of the skills to be learned, the next two involve the designing and optimizing of an action plan for learners to improve their communication and e-presence skills while the fifth module binds them all together by providing for the necessary safeguards in the action plan and letting learners know of the best ways to behave online and seek recourse against unfavourable behaviours. All the course is drafted in the same light to effect consistency and involve a small case study that is gradually applied in an exercise to a greater extend.

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Introducing e-presence:</p> <p>What is e-presence? How does it differ from physical presence? How is e-presence and physical presence combined</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>BLOOMS TAXONOMY</p> <p>Remember An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take always including basic e presence concept and evolution</p> <p>Understand The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will often interrupt the course and take questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts such as famous or infamous bad e-presence results</p> <p>Apply Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by inviting learners to give personal examples offering and inviting conflicting views and attempting to merge them together while trainer gives own personal example on their favourite social media</p>

		<p>personal situation such as with the use of their favourite social media</p> <p>Analyse Trainees will be asked to compare, contrast and differentiate between the real-world examples provided and their personal situation as well as that of their peers. They will be invited to do so also on imaginary scenarios. This will include exercises of finding the mistake in e-presence approaches</p> <p>Evaluate Trainees will be asked to support and defend a course of action and responses given to imaginary scenarios as well as the contrast provided between the different situation described such as with the real-world examples provided. Trainees will be asked to imagine if this situation involve physical presence as opposes to e-presence what would the results and difference be</p> <p>Create Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions. They will note the key differences between e-presence and physical presence and how the two relate</p> <p>SKILLS Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems through the real-world examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these</p>	<p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through relatable Real-world and fictional examples provided explain how e-presence can have very real effects</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner by inviting learners to examine the examples provided and they would have reacted differently using their favourite social media</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to demonstrate how and if there was a change of attitude in the approach, they take on their favourite social media</p>
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		<p>examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved. They will be able to tell what this famous or infamous e-presence examples involved and how they affected physical presence</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill through the personal examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved. This involves considering how trainees can improve their e-presence on their favourite social media</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the fictional examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved. This involves trainees examining the constituent parts of the fictional e-presence and physical presence examples and finding similarities and difference in the two while advising on best approaches to take</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner through the showcasing of how they plan to react to new situation comparing how they reacted to the past. Their favourite social media is enriched by this new approach</p>	
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		<p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the explaining by the learners of the key takeaways they value more and belief will affect their reaction in the future. Trainees will show how their reaction will now be on their favourite social media</p>	
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis Group exercise</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA Actively participates in class exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance Works with peers to deliver a group result</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS Guided discussion, reflection, group exercise, solo exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, what if analysis, open dialogue</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz at home</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary quiz</p>
Module 2	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Introducing Communication: Verbal Communication Nonverbal communication Written communication Communication in the digital era</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>BLOOMS TAXONOMY Remember An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts Followed by a summary part</p>	<p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p>

		<p>at the end of the course revising key take always including basic communication concept and evolution</p> <p>Understand The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will often interrupt the course and take questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts such as famous or infamous bad communication results</p> <p>Apply Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation such as with instances of misunderstanding</p> <p>Analyse Trainees will be asked to compare, contrast and differentiate between the real-world examples provided and their personal situation as well as that of their peers. They will be invited to do so also on imaginary scenarios. This will include exercises of finding the mistake in communication approaches</p> <p>Evaluate Trainees will be asked to support and defend a course of action and responses given to imaginary scenarios as well as the contrast provided between the different situation described such as with the real-world examples provided. Trainees will be asked to imagine if this situation involve verbal communication as opposes to</p>	<p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by inviting learners to give personal examples offering and inviting conflicting views and attempting to merge them together while trainer gives own personal example on miscommunication instances</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through relatable Real-world and fictional examples provided explain how communication can have very real effects</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner by inviting learners to examine the example provided and they would have reacted differently using their new knowledge on communication</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to demonstrate how and if there was a change of attitude in their approach, they take on communication</p>
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		<p>written communication what would the results and difference be</p> <p>Create Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions. They will note the key differences between verbal, written and non-verbal communication and how the three relate</p> <p>SKILLS Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems through the real-world examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved. They will be able to tell what this famous or infamous communication examples involved and how they affected the Real-world</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill through the personal examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved. This involves considering how trainees can improve their communication skills on the verbal, written and nonverbal level</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the fictional examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these</p>	
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		<p>examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved. This involves trainees examining the constituent parts of the fictional communication examples and finding similarities and difference in the two while advising on best approaches to take</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner through the showcasing of how they plan to react to new situation comparing how they reacted to the past. Their ability to communicate is enriched by this new approach</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the explaining by the learners of the key takeaways they value more and belief will affect their reaction in the future. Trainees will show what their reaction will now be on similar future situations</p>	
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis Group exercise</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA Actively participates in class exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS Guided discussion, reflection, group exercise, solo exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, what if analysis, open dialogue</p>

		Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance Works with peers to deliver a group result	
	DAILY EVALUATION Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz quiz	Tasks for Trainees Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz at home	TEACHING METHOD Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary
Module 3	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS e-presence and Communication: Joining the two How does communication affect e-presence and vice versa?	COGNITIVE AREA BLOOMS TAXONOMY Remember An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take aways. A small summary of the previous two modules will be given Understand The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will often interrupt the course and take questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts. The course will also explain how successful online personalities become such Apply Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation. Using their new knowledge, they will complete a draft action plan to improve their media presence through proper communication Analyse	TEACHING METHOD Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by inviting learners to give personal examples offering and inviting conflicting views and attempting to merge them together while an action plan for e-presence and better communication is made New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through relatable Real-world and fictional examples provided explain how communication approaches can have very real effects on e-presence and the physical world

		<p>Trainees will be asked to compare, contrast and differentiate between the real-world examples provided and their personal situation as well as that of their peers. They will be invited to do so also on imaginary scenarios. The learners will contrast the successful online personas and approaches taken by them with their own</p> <p>Evaluate Trainees will be asked to support and defend a course of action and responses given to imaginary scenarios as well as the contrast provided between the different situation described such as with the real-world examples provided.</p> <p>Create Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions. The draft action plan will be discussed with the trainer</p> <p>SKILLS Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems through the real-world examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved through the display of successful and eventually not successful online personas</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill through the personal</p>	<p>New knowledge is applied by the learner by inviting learners to examine the examples provided and they would have reacted differently using their new draft action plan</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to demonstrate how and if there was a change of attitude in the approach, they take on communication</p>
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		<p>examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved by applying on themselves through the action plan their new knowledge on their e-presence and communication methods</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the fictional examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner through the showcasing of how they plan to react to new situation comparing how they reacted to the past with respect to their e-presence and physical presence</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the explaining by the learners of the key takeaways they value more and belief will affect their reaction in the future with respect to both e-presence and the physical world through the use of proper communication techniques</p>	
<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis</p> <p>PRACTICAL AREA</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation</p>		<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Guided discussion, reflection, group exercise, solo exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples,</p>

	<p>Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA</p> <p>Actively participates in class exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance Works with peers to deliver a group result</p>	<p>of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA</p> <p>Actively participates in class exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance Works with peers to deliver a group result</p>	<p>what if analysis, open dialogue</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz Action plan draft Group exercise</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz at home Completes draft of action plan</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <p>Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary applied learning exercise</p>
Module 4	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Optimizing e-presence and communication: Visual presence Non visual presence Best practices on optimizing e-presence and communication</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>BLOOMS TAXONOMY</p> <p>Remember An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take aways. The student will be asked to go over their draft action plan</p> <p>Understand The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will often</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by using the learners action plan to</p>

		<p>interrupt the course and take questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts. Best practice examples on optimizing e-presence and communication will be explained</p> <p>Apply Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation. Based on the best practices, trainees will improve their plan</p> <p>Analyse Trainees will be asked to compare, contrast and differentiate between the best practice examples provided and their personal situation as well as that of their peers. They will be invited to do so also on imaginary scenarios. These will feed in on the final version of their plan</p> <p>Evaluate Trainees will be asked to support and defend a course of action and responses given to imaginary scenarios as well as the contrast provided between the different situation described such as with the real-world examples provided. Trainees will assess the possibility of implementing their action plan and contrast different ideas from their fellows' plans</p> <p>Create Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions. They will</p>	<p>include best practice example in it</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the use of best practice examples that become relatable through their use in their personal action plan for e-presence and communication</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner Through the guided finalisation of the plan</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to express what has changed in their approach following the completion of the action plan</p>
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		<p>finalise their plan having exchanged plans between them for review and set a start date</p> <p>SKILLS Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems through devising their own action plan for e-presence and communication</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill through the best practice's examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the best practice examples provided</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner through the incorporation of the best practices in their action plan</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the implementation of the plan and the techniques described they're in</p>	
<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis preparing learner for future situations</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA</p>		<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Guided discussion, reflection, group exercise, solo exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, what if analysis, open dialogue</p>

		<p>Actively participates in class exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook</p> <p>Presents results in a coherent and systematic way</p> <p>Is open to criticism and discussion</p> <p>Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance</p> <p>Works with peers to deliver a group result</p>	
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Self-evaluation form</p> <p>Mini Quiz</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Completes self-evaluation</p> <p>Complete mini-Quiz at home</p> <p>Completes action plan</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <p>Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary quiz</p>
Module 5	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>E-presence and communication safety: Staying ethical online</p> <p>Digital good manners</p> <p>Recourses to unethical and improper behaviour</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>BLOOMS TAXONOMY</p> <p>Remember</p> <p>An introductory part presenting what is to be learned and key concepts</p> <p>Followed by a summary part at the end of the course revising key take aways. Safety concerns and ethical behaviour are presented as the coat to dress e-presence and communication</p> <p>Understand</p> <p>The delivery of the course will include Real-world examples. The trainer will often interrupt the course and take questions while making clarifications between situations and concepts</p> <p>Apply</p> <p>Trainees will be asked to adapt and demonstrate their new knowledge to their personal situation reflecting bad on behaviour they now view as digitally wrong</p>	<p>Real-world examples are mixed with personal experiences and fictional examples to create a lively discussion and guided form of learner centred approach</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill by inviting learners to give personal examples and reconsidering how safe their behaviour was</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through relatable Real-world and fictional examples provided explain how e-presence and communication can have very real effects and how to improve</p>

		<p>Analyse Trainees will be asked to compare, contrast and differentiate between the real-world examples provided and their personal examples as well as that of their peers. They will be invited to do so also on imaginary scenarios.</p> <p>Evaluate Trainees will be asked to support and defend a course of action and responses given to imaginary scenarios as well as the contrast provided between the different situation described such as with the real-world examples provided.</p> <p>Create Trainees will show how their understanding and behaviour has Improved and how does the new learning relate to their future actions. They will include in their plan recourses for unethical digital behaviour</p> <p>SKILLS Learners are engaged in solving real-world problems through the real-world examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved while also including in their plan the necessary safeguards</p> <p>Existing knowledge and skill are activated as a foundation for new knowledge and skill through the review of their personal examples provided with the new safety concerns</p>	<p>safeguard yourself online</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner by including the safety concern into the action plan</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world by allowing learners to demonstrate if there was a change of attitude in the approach, they take on their e-presence and communication</p>
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		<p>issued to demonstrate how safe previous behaviour was</p> <p>New knowledge is demonstrated to the learner through the fictional examples provided above contrasting different opinions on the impact of these examples and showcasing how it could or if it could be improved following the new set safety precautions</p> <p>New knowledge is applied by the learner through the incorporation of safety concerns in their action plan</p> <p>New knowledge is integrated into the learner's world through the explaining by the learners of the key takeaways they value more and belief will affect their reaction in the future and course taken</p>	
<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Real-world Example analysis Personal Example Analysis Fictional Example Analysis Safeguards in plan</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Provides analysis using new knowledge of real-world examples Recollects and communicates Personal examples within this context Responds to fictional examples with the evaluation of the previous two preparing learner for future situations</p> <p>EDUCATIONAL AREA</p> <p>Actively participates in class exercises, supports position and maintains a more objective outlook Presents results in a coherent and systematic way Is open to criticism and discussion Feels free to ask questions and adheres to trainer's guidance</p>		<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Guided discussion, reflection, group exercise, solo exercise, feedback from peers, feedback from trainer, Real-world examples, fictional example, personal examples, what if analysis, open dialogue</p>

		Works with peers to deliver a group result	
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES	DAILY EVALUATION	TEACHING METHOD
	Self-evaluation form Mini Quiz quiz	Completes self-evaluation Complete mini-Quiz at class	Self-Evaluation, reflection, non-graded summary

E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks.

Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all 5 modules and gain 5 badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

F. REFERENCES

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RO: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-e-presence-and-Communication-RO.pdf>

GE: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-e-presence-and-Communication-DE.pdf>

GR: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-e-presence-and-Communication-GR.pdf>

Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Active Participation

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

Active participation gives individuals greater autonomy in activities and relationships in everyday life, which allows them to live as independently as possible. It also helps individuals increase their autonomy, confidence and self-esteem, and they are more likely to cope with the challenges of the digital world. Active participation refers to the involvement of people in their society, by taking initiatives based on their needs. Being an active citizen shows that we are not passive and we do care about the society we live in. Furthermore, it shows that we do care about others.

The course is divided into two parts: one theoretical and one practical, providing participants with a complex learning process.

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and 5 tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own peace. The 5 modules are:

- Module 1: Digital Citizens in a Digital World
- Module 2: Make your participation outstanding
- Module 3: Freedom to vote
- Module 4: Networking for Advocacy Strategy
- Module 5: Online support with real impact

Essential questions

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	<p>In days / Weeks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ On short term, we expect the trainees to start sharing their ideas, thinking about themselves, expressing opinions effectively. <p>Months</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ On medium term, it is expected to be active in planning, prioritizing and participating in decision-making to make a change.
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<p>Real-life situations / Daily tasks / Regular activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ During their regular activities, trainees will act as active citizen showing that they are not passive and they do care about the society they live in.
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<p>Importance and necessity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ It is important for trainee to understand that active participation is a symbol of independence and democracy. ■ Being involved in such activities enable people to take their own decisions about their lives and to be heard.

What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge and Skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To define the needs of society (digital) ■ To identify different types of online and offline participation ■ To understand what a democratic system is and what its benefits are in a digital world ■ To have a real impact on society due to online methods
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B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

The training is a combination of theoretical lessons accompanied by practical exercises and questionnaires. Tasks to measure students' progress and the level of understanding are gradually introduced throughout the course. During the online course, each participant will have access to a set of educational materials. After successfully solving the tasks, the trainees gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

Course introduction

The course starts with a video presentation to introduce the course and a forum question addressed by course coordinator to help the students become familiar with peers and with the topics of the course.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize hierarchical structures and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational material
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

Upon successful completion of this course, the participants will enjoy the right to be heard, to express their own opinion, and influence decisions affecting them directly.

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Digital citizens in a digital world</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Motivation of doing - What are our needs - What society needs - How society is changing – digitalization 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES</p> <p>Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Be aware of their own needs; ■ Understand the needs of society; ■ Understand the idea of digital society 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Presentation</p>
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES	PRACTICAL AREA	PRACTICAL AREA

	Exercise: What makes you a proper citizen	Go to https://www.bizlibrary.com/s oft-skills-assessment/ Answer the questions Read the explanations	Discussions Brainstorming Exercise Reflection Resume the reflection Debriefing
	DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. We do need digital skills in our digital society	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Describe what you already know about the topic "Active participation" Reply twice to your colleagues' posts	TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection
Module 2	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Make your youth remarkable - What is youth participation - Types of participation - Why be an active citizen - Challenges and obstacles - Examples of youth participation in Europe	COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES Upon completing this module, you will be able to: ■ Define youth participation; ■ Identify different types of participation in the online and offline environment ■ Be aware of their position in helping youth problems in society	TEACHING METHODS Discussions Presentation
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Exercise: Ladder of youth participation	PRACTICAL AREA Draw the ladder of participation; Find a problem that affects your society, especially your life; Draw yourself on the ladder of participation thinking where you situate yourself in resolving this problem	PRACTICAL AREA Discussions Reflection Resume the reflection Debriefing
	DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. Challenges and obstacles	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Identify the challenges and obstacles for youth participation How can we stop these challenges? Discuss with peers	TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection
Module 3	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS The freedom of voting - What is democracy - Our rights in a democratic system - How Europe sees youth nowadays - Digital voting	COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES Upon completing this module, you will be able to: ■ Understand the characteristics of democracy;	TEACHING METHODS Discussions Presentation

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Comprehend the voting system; ■ Use the digital voting system in real-life 	
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Exercise: Online votes are still considered votes?</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Use the Internet and find a country with an online voting system (such as Estonia and e-voting);</p> <p>Write at least 3 advantages of online voting;</p> <p>Write at least 3 disadvantages of online voting</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Debate - someone starts by saying an advantage. Someone else says a disadvantage contesting that advantage.</p> <p>Debriefing</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Quiz</p> <p>Forum. Some people still prefer the traditional way of voting. What would be the reason?</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Share your understanding about people rights in a democratic system via the forum</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Assessment test</p> <p>Forum discussion</p> <p>Self-reflection</p>
Module 4	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Advocacy: networking for advocacy strategy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is a networking - What is advocacy - Understand youth policy - Examples of the advocacy process 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES</p> <p>Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Understand the concept of networking; ■ Comprehend the characteristics of advocacy; ■ Complete an advocacy plan 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Presentation</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Exercise: Our advocacy plan</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Think of a problem you would like to resolve</p> <p>Based on the information about “steps of advocacy”, complete the advocacy plan, trying to resolve your problem</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Exercise</p> <p>Debriefing</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Quiz</p> <p>Forum. Understand the concept of advocacy – Networking for advocacy strategy</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Share your understanding about networking for advocacy</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Assessment test</p> <p>Forum discussion</p> <p>Self-reflection</p>
Module 5	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Online support with real impact</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding community - Online participation 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA ABILITIES</p> <p>Upon completing this module, you will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Be aware of communities’ problems; 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Discussions</p> <p>Presentation</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Principles of online participation - The ladder of online participation - An environment made for youth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Find ways to enrol communities; ■ Make a real impact in society due to online methods 	
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Exercise: Connections online & offline	PRACTICAL AREA Go on http://aspa.ro Investigate their strategy Complete the table (SWOT analysis) regarding their activity online and offline.	PRACTICAL AREA Discussions SWOT Debriefing
	DAILY EVALUATION Quiz Forum. What are the most appropriate ways to enrol online communities	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Express personal opinion about the ways that enrol online communities; Argue personal opinion about this.	TEACHING METHODS Assessment test Forum discussion Self-reflection

E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks.

Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all 5 modules and gain 5 badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

F. REFERENCES:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348231946_Models_of_Youth_Participation_Handbook
<https://resourcecentre.savethechildren.net/library/education-we-want-advocacy-toolkit>
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<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9264-2018-ADD-2/en/pdf>
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Textbooks:

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 RO: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Active-Participation-RO.pdf>
 GE: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Active-Participation-DE.pdf>
 GR: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Active-Participation-GR.pdf>
 Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Rights and Responsibilities

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

Digital citizenship can be a hard concept for youth to grasp in today's digital society, especially when it comes down to the rights and responsibilities we have to adhere to when using the Internet in our everyday lives. In other words, digital citizenship is accompanied by many rights and responsibilities, which refer to those freedoms extended to everyone in a digital world, and which are intended to protect all users as well as everyone else with whom they might interact. This course was developed as a supplement and a tool for trainers to help students understand the different rights and responsibilities people have in today's digital world.

In sum, digital rights are human rights in the digital era. The advent of the internet and information technology has occasioned a change in the way we enjoy and exercise our fundamental rights, such as freedom of expression, access to information, assembly, education and political choice. The term 'digital rights' therefore comprises the rights that are implicated in our access to and use of these technologies. It also necessitates the consideration of the commensurate obligations and responsibilities there are on states and on all users to protect these rights.

The course will introduce trainees the privileges and freedoms extended to all digital technology users, and the behavioural expectations that come with them. It will help them understand that they must act responsibly, ethically and legally as they participate in the digital world. The course will address issues related to copyright laws and plagiarism, as well as the rights all people have as creators of information and media. Cyber bullying and threatening behaviour are two other major issues related to this topic of digital rights and responsibilities, also addressed during the course. Trainees will understand that just as bullying is not tolerated in school and in offline environments, bullying online is not tolerated either. Threatening others through technology is also another inappropriate use of technology, causing hurt and negative effects. The course has been designed to help trainees identify the factors that can intensify online cruelty and cyberbullying as well as create solutions for dealing with cyberbullying situations and for helping others when this occurs. They will become aware of the existing tools and processes to address violations of digital rights and of their responsibilities to counteract when they notice such violations. Overall, the course will empower trainees to protect their digital rights and adhere to their responsibilities in the digital world.

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and 5 tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own pace. The Rights and Responsibilities course is available online and participants can join anytime.

Essential questions

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	In 4 days: <ul style="list-style-type: none">■ To remember the information presented in the course and the ways they can apply their rights and responsibilities in their daily online practices.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To gain the essential knowledge on how their digital rights can be violated and protected ■ To realize the responsibilities, they have for the protection of their digital rights and the digital rights of others. <p>In Weeks/ Months:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To be able to understand and assess their own practices when using digital media and technologies and change them accordingly, in order to respect and protect their digital rights and the digital rights of the other users ■ To know what is accepted and what not when interacting with others online ■ To remember the existing rules and legislation on intellectual property ■ To know the signs and the effects of cyberbullying, online sexual harassment, and online hate speech and the ways to address this phenomenon ■ To know how to report different violations of their digital rights and the digital rights of others ■ To remember the importance and the necessity of the freedom of expression, as an important digital right, and the limits of this freedom ■ To understand what constitutes hate speech and the means to address it and combat it when it occurs during their online life ■ To learn to avoid plagiarism, to respect copyright, and to use digital hardware and networks ethically and within the law ■ To know what constitutes a safe and secure behaviour when online ■ To show respect for shared ideas and fairly treat resources created and shared via the internet ■ To adhere to certain rules and policies when creating, sharing, commenting digital content and when interacting online with others on social media and in the digital world, in general.
<p>How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?</p>	<p>The course is expected to have enduring value for trainees in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Real-life situations, ■ Daily tasks and ■ Regular online activities <p>More specifically, trainees will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Know how to interact and communicate with others online ethically, legally and safely ■ Apply relevant rules, legislations and regulations in their studying and/or working practices

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Know and apply good and respectful digital behaviours and avoid negative and dangerous ones ■ Be empowered to address and report incidents related to cyberbullying and hate speech online ■ Value their digital rights such as the freedom of expression and online safety ■ Know what endangers and/or constitutes a violation of their digital rights, especially their right to privacy ■ Be aware of their own practices related to their digital rights and responsibilities ■ To assess their online behaviours and practices and how to amend them for their own benefit ■ Know where to turn in case they feel that their rights are violated or when others' digital rights are not respected
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The importance of assessing and adjusting practices and behaviours related to digital means in order to respect the digital rights of all users ■ The necessity of a respectful, legal and ethical online behaviour ■ The connection between human rights and digital rights and responsibilities ■ The extent to which digital rights and responsibilities affect our offline life ■ The significance of issues related to digital rights and responsibilities, such as cyberbullying, intellectual property, online privacy and hate speech ■ The necessity to identify and counteract to what constitutes a threat to or a violation of digital rights.
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge: Trainees will develop knowledge on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Their own digital rights and responsibilities ■ The practices and behaviours which respect and adhere to these rights ■ The practices and behaviours which constitute a violation of these rights (cyberbullying, online sexual harassment and online hate speech) ■ The identification of ethical and legal online behaviours and their opposites ■ The actions which need to be taken in cases of violation of digital rights ■ The services they can contact in case of violation of their digital rights ■ How to protect their digital rights ■ How to fulfil their digital responsibilities <p>Skills: Trainees will develop:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Critical and analytical thinking ■ Decision taking skills ■ Self- respect and respect for others and their work, their views and their attitudes ■ Social skills (for both online and offline environments) ■ Creativity ■ Skills related to the evaluation of the accuracy, the perspective, and the validity of digital media and social posts ■ Communication skills with a special focus on respect and empathy
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B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

The training is a combination of a theoretical section and practical activities accompanied by infographics, exercises and questionnaires. Tasks to measure students' progress and the development of the relevant skills and knowledge are gradually introduced throughout the course. During the online course, each participant will have access to a set of educational materials (such as presentations, articles, videos and relevant web pages). After successfully solving the tasks, the trainees gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

The course will implement and apply all Merrill's principles of the instruction:

- Problem-orientation: learners deal with issues of real-life. For example, case studies will be based on real-life stories.
- Activation: prior knowledge of learners is used to activate new knowledge. For example, in the beginning of each module, trainees will fill in a tool on the basic thematic areas of the module, so that the trainer proceeds accordingly
- Demonstration: new knowledge is shown to learners. For example, in every course module the trainer will use presentations to discuss the module theme.
- Application: new knowledge or skills are used to solve a problem. For example, in almost every module a real-life situation related to specific violations of digital rights will be presented and discussed, so that trainees apply their knowledge to address the situation.
- Integration: learners use new knowledge or skills in their real-life. For example, assignments will be given to trainees, so that they apply and integrate what they have learned in their own online practices.

Course introduction

1.5-2 min video presentation to introduce the course, by the trainer. Alternatively, a short quiz will be introduced to activate the trainees' interest and to help them assess and think on their own practices related to their health and wellbeing when using digital means and technologies.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize learning and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational materials
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).

- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).
- The course documentation is written in EN/ RO/GE/GR.

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the course is for trainees to understand their own digital rights and responsibilities and the ways they are connected to the broader area of digital citizenship. The main objective is also related to the development of the relevant skills to respect and promote digital rights and responsibilities.

More specific objectives include the development of certain knowledge and skills, so that trainees will:

- Understand the meaning and the importance of digital rights and responsibilities
- Be able to identify practices and behaviours which respect digital rights or violate them
- Realize the key issues related to online safety and privacy
- Apply legal and ethical behaviour when studying, working and interacting with others online
- Become familiar with the ways to counteract to incidents of cyberbullying, online sexual harassment and hate speech
- Understand the connection and interdependence between online and offline conduct
- Be sure on the available means and ways to report alarming online phenomena such as identity thefts and threats
- Realize the necessity of respecting digital rights and fulfilling digital responsibilities and obligations
- Modify their online behaviours according to the newly acquired knowledge on digital rights and responsibilities.

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Introduction to digital rights and responsibilities.</p> <p>Basic concepts to be introduced in this module are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - human rights - fundamental rights - children's rights - digital rights (basic elements and concepts), digital responsibilities (basic elements and concepts) and their connection 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identify the connection between human rights and digital rights - match digital rights with the responsibilities these rights result in - explain the necessity to respect digital rights - recognize the positive effects of respecting digital rights - identify the most common violations of digital rights - give examples on how to address and counteract when such violations occur. <p>SKILLS</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p>	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life problems and behaviours to guide students to acquire knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. The questions can be asked after the self- check quiz to promote dialogue and

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - positive results when respecting digital rights and when adhering to digital responsibilities - basic dangers for/ violations of digital rights and ways to address them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain the significance of digital rights and responsibilities - identify the areas where digital rights and responsibilities relate to - categorize those digital rights which are commonly violated or neglected - judge the behaviours related to violations of digital rights - determine the interconnection between online and offline rights and responsibilities. 	<p>exchange of prior experiences in order to develop new skills related to digital rights and responsibilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote experiential learning, cooperation and respect.
<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Class activity:</p> <p>Trainees take up a short quiz (developed by the trainer) to check existing skills and knowledge on digital rights and responsibilities. After completing the quiz, trainees share the results with the class and comment on the findings (face-to-face or online via forum).</p> <p>The trainer shows one of the following short videos on digital rights and responsibilities:</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xjdu-NII4y8&ab_channel=EdieRadionov</p> <p>or</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zi8cik98YmE&ab_channel=JanyTaylor</p> <p>which introduce viewers to these concepts. After watching the videos, the trainer can initiate a discussion on them</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize and describe different digital rights and responsibilities - structure the content and ideas - identify legal and respectful online behaviours and their opposites - discuss the prevalence of digital rights to all online environments and interactions - consider their own practices related to digital rights and responsibilities - propose ways for the respect and protection of certain digital rights <p>Analysis of statistical data on the digital habits of young people regarding the respect or violation of digital rights (country specific/ globally)</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic using a quiz (already prepared) or a discussion - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings - presents and comments recent statistical data on the common violations of digital rights - relates the concepts of digital rights and responsibilities to everyday real-life behaviours - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions

	and ask trainees to recognize the digital rights and responsibilities that were mentioned during the videos. (Extra questions: Would they add more? what was the most striking piece of information on the videos?)		
	DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees: - answer the questions posed at the forum - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting	TEACHING METHODS Forum
Module 2	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Copyright issues During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed: - rights and responsibilities when reproducing or distributing someone else's work (text/ photo/ recording/ etc) - existing laws to protect copyright - the logic and the implementation of every copyright policy in educational or professional environments - the consequences of breaking copyright law	COGNITIVE AREA Trainees should be able to: - understand the importance of copyrights issues in everyday tasks and activities - realize the connection between digital rights and responsibilities and copyright - identify cases when copyright is not respected - determine the reasons and the consequences when violating copyright issues - determine the correct ways to address copyright issues SKILLS Trainees should be able to: - evaluate cases related to the respect or violation of copyright - analyse the consequences of violating copyright in education and work - recommend the best ways to deal with copyright issues	TEACHING METHOD - The trainer uses real-life problems and behaviours to guide students to acquire knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote experiential learning, cooperation and respect - The trainer presents the basic concepts related to copyright and initiates

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the moral issues related to copyright - different licensing models (e.g. creative commons) - plagiarism and its consequences 		discussions on the responsibilities related to copyright.
<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Class activity: Trainees take up the following quiz https://inside.senecacollege.ca/mylearning/TLP/CopyrightQuiz_FINAL_-_Storyline_output/story.html5.html to test their knowledge on copyright. They share their answers with the rest of the class and provide the trainer a clear idea on the trainees'; existing knowledge in order to build it up. The trainer can also show the following video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XzzkSZ0Jrko&ab_channel=GCFLearnFree.org in order to activate students and introduce them to the issues related to copyright. The trainer can initiate discussions based on the information presented in the video.</p>	<p>Tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize which behaviours and practices align with existing rules, laws and policies related to copyright - understand the different sectors where copyright can be violated - analyse the consequences when copyright is not respected - relate copyright in the online and offline world - express their concerns and objections for the violation of copyright - give examples of licensing models - interpret copyright laws, acts, regulations in their own environments <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply knowledge on copyright to their education/ work environment - respect the work of others - recommend solutions to avoid copyright violations and plagiarism - determine the originality of an item produced (text, image, song, etc) 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic using a quiz or a discussion - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings - presents and comments recent statistical data on the common violations of copyright issues - relates the concept of copyright to everyday real-life behaviours - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions - briefly presents laws, acts and regulations for the protection of copyright
DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees:	TEACHING METHODS Forum

	Or A short quiz to check the acquisition of the relevant skills and knowledge	- answer the questions posed at the forum/ quiz - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting	Or quiz
Module 3	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Online sexual harassment</p> <p>During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the extent of the phenomenon of online sexual harassment - the connection between online and offline harassment - the gender perspective of the online harassment - the causes and effects of online harassment - the ways to respond to online sexual harassment - the ways that online harassment violates certain digital rights - the effective and efficient reporting routes available 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand what types of behaviour constitute online sexual harassment - define the term online sexual harassment - explore the gendered context in which online sexual harassment takes place. - understand their school/setting's reporting process - explore the challenges young people face in reporting online sexual harassment - identify the positive effects reporting can have <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand the emotional impact online sexual harassment can have on those involved - recognize examples of online sexual harassment - recognize examples of victim-blaming in response to online sexual harassment. - respond to incidences of online sexual harassment in a sympathetic, helpful and supportive manner. - recognize the reporting routes available to them and choose the most relevant one, per case 	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life problems and instances of online harassment to guide students to acquire relevant knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote experiential learning, cooperation and respect - The trainer presents the basic concepts related to online sexual harassment and initiates discussions on the responsibilities for reporting such incidents - The trainer can also use role playing to activate trainees' interest and raise their awareness on the issue.
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Class activity</p> <p>The trainer presents a series of cases/</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - respond to the presentation of incidents to recognize incidents on online harassment 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about

<p>incidents/ conversations/ behaviours, among which some can be characterized as online sexual harassment and some not. The trainer asks trainees to recognize the ones that are actually online sexual harassment and initiates a discussion on their common characteristics, in order to achieve a consensus on a definition and the types of online harassment.</p> <p>The trainer can show the following video https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bL8FOYyR3dk&ab_channel=hildnetInternational and initiate a discussion to help trainees identify, define and understand what online sexual harassment is.</p> <p>The trainer can share a real-life online sexual harassment incident and ask students how they would respond if they were witnesses of the incident</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - support their choices in a logical manner - participate in the discussions to define and identify online harassment - contemplate on the different means to respond to such incidents and the effective ways to report them - check their own reactions to these incidents and evaluate them - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ability to make the connection between rights and responsibilities in the digital world and the alarming phenomenon of online harassment - apply their existing knowledge to understand something new - evaluate different incidents and different responses to incidents regarding online harassment - judge and critically evaluate their own behaviours when witnessing such incidents 	<p>the topic through a discussion on different cases of harassment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings on the identity, severity, forms and dangers of online (sexual) harassment - presents and comments recent statistical data on online sexual harassment - relates the concept of online sexual harassment to everyday real-life behaviours - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions - briefly presents laws, acts and regulations for addressing and reporting such incidents - discusses issues related to online sexual harassment, such as gender identity, victim blaming, slut shaming, etc.
<p>DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply Or A short quiz to check the acquisition of the</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees: - answer the questions posed at the forum/ quiz - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS Forum Or quiz</p>

	relevant skills and knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting - research on the services available to report online sexual harassment in their country 	
Module 4	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Cyberbullying</p> <p>During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the connection of cyberbullying with digital rights and responsibilities - cyberbullying as a form of discrimination - forms and types of cyberbullying - causes and effects of cyberbullying - the roles of the basic actors: the victim, the perpetrator, the bystander (witness) - the human/ moral and the legal response to cyberbullying - the importance of empathy and the consideration of other people's feelings - ways to prevent cyberbullying and other forms of negative, rude, or mean behaviour 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand and identify what types of behaviour constitute cyberbullying - distinguish between polite and respectful online behaviour and rude behaviour - consider the effects of cyberbullying to the victims and to the witnesses - explain the connection between online and offline bullying - determine the actions to be taken in response to cyberbullying - recognize the importance of empathy <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organize a response to cyberbullying incidents - evaluate online behaviours and judge them on the basis of the characteristics of cyberbullying - develop skills related to active listening and empathy - recommend ways to respond and report cyberbullying phenomena - select the effective ways to encourage and empower victims and bystanders to counteract when cyberbullying occurs. 	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life problems and instances of cyberbullying to guide students to acquire relevant knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote experiential learning, cooperation and respect - The trainer presents the basic concepts related to cyberbullying and initiates discussions on the responsibilities for reporting such incidents - The trainer can also use role-playing to activate trainees' interest and raise their awareness on the issue. - The trainer can show short videos made by organizations (e.g. educational institutes, police, etc) for the prevention and reporting of cyberbullying.

	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Class activity</p> <p>The trainer presents a series of cases/ incidents/ conversations/ behaviours, which include cyberbullying cases. The trainer initiates a discussion on the forms and types of cyberbullying. He she can use the following video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0Xo8N9qIJtk&ab_channel=Kaspersky</p> <p>The trainer shows the following video to demonstrate how a cyberbullying incident can escalate and what effects it can have on the victim: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LC1BYXkHG3A&ab_channel=AronAttwell</p> <p>The trainer asks students to respond to specific cases studies and explain how they would react if they were witnesses of these cases.</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - respond to the presentation of incidents to recognize incidents of cyberbullying - support their choices in a logical manner - participate in the discussions to define and identify cyberbullying - contemplate on the different means to respond to such incidents and the effective ways to report them - check their own reactions to these incidents and evaluate them - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ability to make the connection between rights and responsibilities in the digital world and the alarming phenomenon of cyberbullying - apply their existing knowledge to understand something new - evaluate different incidents and different responses to incidents regarding cyberbullying - judge and critically evaluate their own behaviours when witnessing such incidents - develop the skills to respond to cyberbullying as victims and as witnesses - become empowered to address such incidents 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic through a discussion on different cases of cyberbullying - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings on the identity, severity, forms and dangers of cyberbullying - presents and comments recent statistical data on cyberbullying, providing age specific findings - relates the concept of cyberbullying to everyday real-life behaviours - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions - briefly presents the ways for addressing and reporting such incidents - discusses the important role of the bystanders to combat the phenomenon - focus on empathy when interacting with others online
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Forum posts and reply</p> <p>Or</p> <p>A short quiz to check the acquisition of the relevant skills and knowledge</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - answer the questions posed at the forum/ quiz - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Forum</p> <p>Or</p> <p>quiz</p>

		- research on the services available to report online sexual harassment in their country	
Module 5	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Online hate speech</p> <p>During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the meaning and the different forms of online hate speech - hate speech as a violation of digital rights - the responsibilities of users when hate speech is encountered online - the connection between hate speech with racism, xenophobia, sexism and other forms of discrimination - the reasons and the effects of online hate speech - the ways to respond to online hate speech 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand and describe the relationship between hate speech and xenophobia (and other forms of discrimination) - analyse how the internet has contributed to an increase in hate speech and extremist views - describe ways to use the internet to combat the different types of hate speech - identify specific actions to positively affect a situation involving hate speech - recognize incidents of hate speech on social media and new media - recommend ways to empower victims and minimize online hate speech <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - evaluate the short term and long-term effects of online hate speech to victims and to users in general - select behaviours to combat hate speech online - analyse the ways to address online hate speech when encountered 	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life problems and instances of online hate speech to guide students to acquire relevant knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote experiential learning, cooperation and respect - The trainer presents the basic concepts related to online hate speech and initiates discussions on the responsibilities for reporting such incidents - The trainer can also use role-playing to activate trainees' interest and raise their awareness on the issue. - The trainer can show short videos made by organizations (e.g. educational institutes, police, etc) for the prevention and reporting of online hate speech.
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Class activity</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Trainees:</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>The trainer:</p>

	<p>The trainer asks trainees to provide different examples of hate speech they have witnessed online. The trainer presents a series of cases/ incidents/ conversations/ behaviours, which include cases of online hate speech and asks trainees to distinguish them.</p> <p>Watch the video https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1_yrY2fOazE&ab_channel=Era with different forms of hate speech and the connection between freedom of expression and hate speech.</p> <p>The trainer discusses with trainees the causes of hate speech connecting it to sexism, racism, homophobia, and other forms of discrimination. In small groups the trainer asks trainees to think of different ways to react to different forms of hate speech and evaluate them.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - respond to the presentation of incidents to recognize incidents of online hate speech - support their choices in a logical manner - participate in the discussions to define and identify online hate speech - contemplate on the different means to respond to such incidents and the effective ways to report them - check their own reactions to these incidents and evaluate them - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ability to make the connection between rights and responsibilities in the digital world and the alarming phenomenon of online hate speech among youth - apply their existing knowledge to understand something new - evaluate different incidents and different responses to incidents regarding online hate speech - judge and critically evaluate their own behaviours when witnessing such incidents - develop the skills to respond to online hate speech as victims and as witnesses - become empowered to address such incidents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic through a discussion on different cases of online hate speech - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings on the identity, severity, forms and dangers of online hate speech - presents and comments recent statistical data on online hate speech, providing age specific findings - relates the concept of online hate speech to everyday real-life behaviours also violating human rights - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions - briefly presents the ways for addressing and reporting such incidents - discusses the important role of the witnesses to combat the phenomenon - focus on empathy when interacting with others online
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Forum posts and reply</p> <p>Or</p> <p>A short quiz to check the acquisition of the relevant skills and knowledge</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - answer the questions posed at the forum/ quiz - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Forum</p> <p>Or</p> <p>quiz</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting - research on the services available to report online sexual harassment in their country 	
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E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks.

Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all 5 modules and gain 5 badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

F. REFERENCES

Young, Kimberly. (2009). Internet Addiction: Diagnosis and Treatment Considerations. Journal of Contemporary Psychotherapy. 39. 241-246. 10.1007/s10879-009-9120-x.
<https://www.common sense.org/education/digital-citizenship/lesson/countering-hate-speech-online>
<https://tlp-lpa.ca/digital-citizenship/harassment>
<http://dematteisdigitalcitizenship.weebly.com/digital-rights--responsibilities.html>
<https://www.childnet.com/resources/step-up-speak-up/teaching-toolkit/teaching-guide>
<https://tlp-lpa.ca/digital-citizenship/copyright>
<https://sites.google.com/a/aea11.k12.ia.us/heartland-digital-citizenship/rights-responsibilities>
<https://www.rockyview.ab.ca/21stC/supporting/websafety/digital-citizenship/nine-elements/digital-rights-and-responsibilities>
<https://www.common sense.org/education/digital-citizenship/curriculum?topic=cyberbullying-digital-drama--hate-speech&grades=11,12,10>
<https://eduwebinar.com.au/digital-rights-responsibilities/>
<https://peru.instructure.com/courses/2513/pages/digital-rights-and-responsibilities>
<http://digitalrightsandresponsibilities.weebly.com/>
<http://areyouadigitalcitizen.weebly.com/digital-rights-and-responsibilities.html>

Textbooks:

EN: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Rights-and-Responsibilities.pdf>
 RO: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Rights-and-Responsibilities-RO.pdf>
 GE: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Rights-and-Responsibilities-DE.pdf>
 GR: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Rights-and-Responsibilities-GR.pdf>
 Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Privacy and Security

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

Privacy and security are old terms, but their importance only grew in recent years. They are especially important for younger people who spend a significant amount of time in digital environments. A holistic teaching approach to media literacy and the concept of digital citizenship requires knowledge and routine in relation to privacy and security. This model course will help teachers to explain the fundamental aspects of privacy and security and their importance to people's well-being. It will support teachers with ideas for content and exercises to improve the comprehension and promote the awareness on privacy matters in the digital era.

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and 5 tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own peace. The Privacy and Security course is available online and participants can join anytime.

Essential questions

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	<p>In days:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Remembering most or all information around privacy itself, its importance, its need for protection through adequate security measures ■ Realizing the importance of privacy to their own well-being and future security ■ Remembering specific security measures <p>In weeks/months:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Being always conscious about sharing personal data and information when being online ■ Having security measures engrained as a natural part of their everyday life processes and actions ■ Supporting friends and family by providing information and aid in relation to privacy protection ■ Actively supporting the protection of privacy as a member of the civil society and a responsible digital citizen
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<p>In Real-life situations/Daily tasks/Regular activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Always being conscious about privacy ensures that they do not publish personal data or information that might harm their future occupational chances. ■ Their knowledge and skills make them more reliable as friends and co-workers. ■ They are better equipped to critically deal with new digital inventions, devices, and concepts regarding their privacy.
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<p>Importance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ How deeply linked privacy is to one's well-being and free development of personality. ■ Therefore, how important the protection of privacy is.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Keeping privacy protected is a societal task and needs broad support. <p>Necessity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The continuous necessity of upholding privacy rights especially in times when privacy threatens to become an afterthought in the process of digital innovations
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge/Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The definition of privacy and specifics about privacy in digital environments. ■ The importance of maintaining a constant awareness of security risks. ■ Fundamental security measures for the protection of privacy.

B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

This course is a combination of theoretical lessons given by the trainer with the support of pictures/graphics, explanatory videos, and live demonstrations on the www. It will follow the characteristics of learner-centred pedagogy and will rely and build up on previous experiences of the students. The course will encourage active participation by using practical exercises for groups or for individuals, quizzes, and feedback questionnaires. The course modules will gradually increase the level of pre-required knowledge by following the five stages of the 5E Model and constructively lead students to new knowledge and insights. During the online course, each student will have access to a set of educational materials. After successfully solving the tasks of a module, the students gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

Course introduction

Either a short video presentation by the trainer or a fact/example concerning privacy issues in relation to widely used digital platforms will be shown to kickstart an active reflection of the own behaviour.

Teaching medium

- Outlines and infographics to organize hierarchical structures and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational material.
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).
- The course documentation is written in EN/RO/DE/GR.

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

The main course objective is to transmit an understanding of the core, the values, and the importance of privacy in the context of human rights, free development of personality and the over well-being of an individual. This objective is related to the development of fundamental security measurement skills that the participants need to understand and apply to protect their and others privacy.

The main course objective can be broken down as follows:

- Understand the definition of privacy
- Recognize the importance of privacy
- Explain the importance of privacy
- Understand the definition of security
- Recognize the importance of security
- Explain the importance of security in context of privacy
- Understand the definition of digital environments
- Recognize the influence of social network sites
- Identify the multi-layered threats to privacy in digital environments
- Understand the role of hardware and software in digital environments
- Identify the individual risks of using hardware and software
- Recognize user-related risks in relation to the usage of hardware and software
- Recall the basic means of security in digital environments
- Develop a basic security strategy to protect one's and other persons' privacy
- Develop an attitude that promotes conscious and responsible online behaviours and interactions
- Apply security measures to one's devices, accounts, and digital interactions

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Introduction to privacy</p> <p>Presenting its importance as a human right, its role in legislation, its heightened importance in digital environments.</p>	<p>The learner should be able to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand the definition of privacy - recognize the importance of privacy 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>All modules follow the characteristics of learner-centred pedagogy.</p> <p>Based on the 5E Model: Engage (1E) and find out about prior experiences with privacy. Set them in relation to basic revelations on privacy made in this module.</p> <p>Activities and material: Padlet (before the course), brainstorming, pictures</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Group work/World café; can take place face2face or virtually: discuss topics and</p>	<p>The learner should be able to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand personal habits in relation to privacy 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Based on the 5E Model:</p>

	present results in relation to privacy in small groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize potential risks resulting from those habits in relation to privacy - recognize current regulations 	<p>Explore (2E) by confronting the students with different topics to explore their new knowledge and their pre-experiences.</p> <p>Activities and material: discussion in world café, pen and paper</p>
	DAILY EVALUATION Short quiz Forum activity	TASKS FOR TRAINEES - finish the quiz - answer questions in the forum and interact with others	TEACHING METHODS Quiz Forum
Module 2	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Introduction to security Presenting the fundamental of security, its relation to privacy and its importance in digital environments.	The learner should be able to - understand the definition of security - explain the need for security in the digital era	Based on the 5E Model: Engage (1E) and find out about prior experiences with security. Set them in relation to basic revelations on security made in this module. Activities and material: brainstorming, pictures, videos, Real-world problems
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Mapping exercise; can take place face2face or virtually: Assign different types of personal data to different levels of acceptable public exposure.	The learner should be able to - understand the difference between personal data and public data - Recognize their preferences in relation to the publication of personal data - Justify the usage of their personal data	Based on the 5E Model: Engage (1E) and explore (2E) by encouraging the students to share their experiences and confront them with different topics to explore their new knowledge and their pre-experiences
	DAILY EVALUATION Short quiz Forum activity	TASKS FOR TRAINEES - finish the quiz - answer questions in the forum and interact with others	TEACHING METHODS Quiz Forum
Module 3	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS	The learner should be able to	Based on the 5E Model:

	<p>Privacy in a digital environment</p> <p>Explaining the technical and societal background of digital environments, the overwhelming influence of digital environments and their risks in relation to privacy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand the definition of digital environments - recognize the influence of digital environments - identify the privacy risks of digital environments - identify the risks of being and interacting online - identify the relation between digital platforms and personal data 	<p>Explain (3E) and relate their knowledge to the first two modules in relation to privacy and security.</p> <p>Activities and material: website, explanatory videos, discussion</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Small group work; can take place face2face or virtually: In groups, choose a social media website like Facebook or Instagram. Research on different privacy functions and settings currently applying to the site and present them to the plenum.</p>	<p>The learner should be able to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand how privacy is handled by social media websites - understand how online communities affect privacy - apply security measures to their social media account 	<p>Based on the 5E Model: Elaborate (4E) and investigate privacy settings in real accounts. Investigate the privacy and security behaviour of social networks in relation to the modules 1-3.</p> <p>Activities and material: devices with active internet connection, discussion, real-life research, presentation</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Short quiz Forum activity</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - finish the quiz - answer questions in the forum and interact with others 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Quiz Forum</p>
Module 4	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Security risks in a digital environment</p> <p>Explaining the roles of hardware and software in electronic devices. Presenting existing threats to hardware and software and the special role of user-related risks.</p>	<p>The learner should be able to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand the role of hardware and software - identify the security risks associated to hardware and software - recognize user-related risks in relation to hardware and software usage 	<p>Based on the 5E Model: Explain (3E) and relate the new knowledge to module 2 and reflect its impact on privacy concerns.</p> <p>Activities and material: website, explanatory videos, discussion</p>
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Roleplay exercise; can take place face2face or virtually: Playing the role of an attacker who gained access to one's</p>	<p>The learner should be able to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand why device security is important - identify the consequences of weak security 	<p>Based on the 5E Model: Elaborate (4E) and investigate existing problems with one's own security</p>

	smartphone or computer. What could the attacker learn and which harm could they cause?	- analyse own security weak points	behaviour. Engrain the importance of security. Activities and material: own devices with active internet connection, discussion, independent analysis and reflection, presentation
	DAILY EVALUATION Short quiz Forum activity	TASKS FOR TRAINEES - finish the quiz - answer questions in the forum and interact with others	TEACHING METHODS Quiz Forum
Module 5	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Security tips for the digital environment Presenting the fundamentals rules for a secure handling of hardware and software as a responsible, informed digital citizen. Elaborating on user-related privacy issues.	The learner should be able to - recall the basic means of security in digital environments. - develop a basic security strategy to protect their and other people's privacy - develop an attitude that promotes conscious and responsible online behaviours and interactions - apply security measures to their devices, accounts, and digital interactions	Based on the 5E Model: Elaborate (4E) and apply the knowledge from module 4 to gain a deep understanding of necessary security measures. Activities and material: website, explanatory videos, discussion
	PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Presentation exercise; can take place face2face or virtually: Imaging that an inexperienced friend needs with protecting their privacy. Presenting the most important security measures for different scenarios.	The learner should be able to - understand why security is important - present the most important security measures	Based on the 5E Model: Evaluate (5E) and observe during this exercise how deep the understanding of privacy and security goes and how the students cope with the presented situation. Activities and material: problem solving and critical thinking, presentation, discussion
	DAILY EVALUATION Short quiz Forum activity	TASKS FOR TRAINEES - finish the quiz	TEACHING METHODS Quiz Forum

		- answer questions in the forum and interact with others	
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E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks.

Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all 5 modules and gain 5 badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

F. REFERENCES

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<https://www.coe.int/en/web/digital-citizenship-education/-/digital-citizenship-education-overview-and-new-perspectives>

<https://www.common sense.org/education/digital-citizenship/curriculum?topic=privacy--security>

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Textbooks:

EN: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Privacy-and-Security.pdf>

RO: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Privacy-and-Security-RO.pdf>

GE: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Privacy-and-Security-DE.pdf>

GR: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Privacy-and-Security-GR.pdf>

Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Consumer Awareness

A. COURSE OVERVIEW

Course description

The Internet, with all its dimensions like social media or other virtual spaces, includes environments where often the fact of being a digital citizen means also being a user, being a consumer. Understanding the dimensions connected to this issue is one of competences that future individuals need to have if they want to navigate safely in these digital environments, especially since these dimensions are connected to digital citizenship and democratic participation.

The aim of the course is to cover the most important dimensions of consumer awareness in the digital world, such as:

- Consumer activism which has supported the emergence of new businesses in line with certain core values such as environmentally friendly business practices or supporting the local economy,
- The emergence of new forms of consumer participation thanks to technology such as crowdfunding platforms,
- The emergence of new business models which escape consumer awareness, namely, business models relying on data for various purposes, such as targeted advertising for search engines or social networks,
- The limits of consumer power and the attempts at misleading or manipulating online consumers (for example, via green-washing, targeted advertising and monopolies or dominant market players locking consumers into certain consumption patterns by restricting consumer choices),
- The rights all people shopping online have as consumers and the application of those rights and responsibilities if products and services exploit and/or infringe the rights of others,
- The fact that digital citizens are also acting as entrepreneurs, actively selling products and services to digital citizen consumers using social media to market their goods, online platforms to host their goods, digital delivery systems to ship their goods,
- Existing consumer protection policies and frameworks which are effective and responsive to the interconnected nature of e-commerce

Course structure

The course comprises five asynchronous teaching modules (theoretical, infographics, video and ppt), five synchronous training exercises (workshops, case studies) and 5 tasks that can be solved by individuals on their own pace. The Consumer Awareness course is available online and participants can join anytime.

Essential questions

Key questions	Results
What do you want your trainees to remember and learn to do 4 days, weeks, or months from now?	In 4 days: <ul style="list-style-type: none">■ To remember the information presented in the course and the ways they can apply their rights and responsibilities as consumers in their daily online practices.■ To gain the essential knowledge on how their rights as consumers can be violated and protected■ To realize the responsibilities, they have for the protection of their digital rights as consumers as well as the available means to protect these rights.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To remember the techniques used in digital advertising and the role it plays in consumer behaviours and patterns ■ To remember the basic rights and responsibilities when becoming or being a digital entrepreneur <p>In Weeks/ Months:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To be able to understand and assess their own practices when using digital media and technologies to consume products or services ■ To know what is accepted and what not when selling or buying products online ■ To remember the existing rules and legislation for the protection of consumer rights ■ To know how to report different violations of their digital rights as consumers ■ To know what constitutes a safe and secure behaviour when selling or buying online ■ To know how to transact online securely, being aware of consumer terms and conditions ■ To apply security measures when shopping online ■ To avoid misleading information and scams
How will this have enduring value for trainees beyond the classroom?	<p>The course is expected to have enduring value for trainees in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Real-life situations, ■ Daily tasks and ■ Regular online activities <p>More specifically, trainees will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ know how to make online transactions ethically, legally and safely ■ apply relevant rules, legislations and regulations when buying or selling products online ■ understand the techniques used to mislead and manipulate consumers online ■ know how to report violations of their rights as digital consumers ■ understand the role of digital advertising and how it affects consumers' behaviour ■ know what endangers and/or constitutes a violation of their digital rights as consumers ■ be aware of their own practices related to searching and buying online ■ know where to turn in case they feel that their rights as consumers are violated or when others' digital rights are not respected
What should trainees understand about the topic?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The importance of making well informed decisions when buying products online ■ The fact that companies are accountable for what they sell and how they sell it

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ The potential concerns or issues which they might encounter while purchasing, and the necessity of a logical viewpoint ■ The different dimensions and implications of product liability and consumer protection. ■ The interconnection between consumer awareness online and offline ■ The connection between consumer awareness to life skills, self-confidence and quality of life ■ The need to prevent the propagation of misleading and ambiguous messages regarding the characteristics of the products sold online ■ The role of certain authorities and organizations protecting their rights as consumers
What key knowledge and skills will trainees acquire at the end of the lesson?	<p>Key knowledge: Trainees will develop knowledge on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Their own digital rights and responsibilities as consumers and/or entrepreneurs in online environments ■ The practices and behaviours which companies should follow in order to respect and adhere to these rights ■ The practices and behaviours which constitute a violation of these rights, including targeted advertising ■ Their right to be protected against products, production processes and services that endanger their physical health or wellbeing ■ The ways to be protected against exploitation when making online purchases ■ How to achieve secure online consumption <p>Skills: Trainees will develop:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Critical and analytical thinking ■ Decision taking skills ■ Self- respect and self confidence ■ Social skills (for both online and offline environments) ■ Creativity ■ Skills related to the evaluation of the accuracy, the perspective, and the validity of digital advertising ■ Awareness on how to protect personal information when buying online ■ Skills related to identifying commercial persuasion and being able to interpret, analyse and critically evaluate commercial messages

B. STATEMENT OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Training methodology

The training is a combination of a theoretical section and practical activities accompanied by infographics, exercises and questionnaires. Tasks to measure students' progress and the development of the relevant skills and knowledge are gradually introduced throughout the course. During the online course, each participant will have access to a set of educational materials (such as presentations,

articles, videos and relevant web pages). After successfully solving the tasks, the trainees gain badges and are granted with access to the next module.

The course will implement and apply all Merrill's principles of the instruction:

- Problem-orientation: learners deal with issues of real-life. For example, case studies will be based on real-life stories.
- Activation: prior knowledge of learners is used to activate new knowledge. For example, in the beginning of each module, trainees will fill in a tool on the basic thematic areas of the module, so that the trainer proceeds accordingly
- Demonstration: new knowledge is shown to learners. For example, in every course module the trainer will use presentations to discuss the module theme. Moreover, the trainer will create opportunities to demonstrate certain online behaviours to be selected (or avoided)
- Application: new knowledge or skills are used to solve a problem. For example, in almost every module a real-life situation related to specific violations of consumers rights will be presented and discussed, so that trainees apply their knowledge to address the situation.
- Integration: learners use new knowledge or skills in their real-life. For example, assignments will be given to trainees, so that they apply and integrate what they have learned in their own online practices.

Course introduction

1.5-2 min video presentation to introduce the course, by the trainer. Alternatively, a short quiz will be introduced to activate the trainees' interest and to help them assess and think on their own practices related to their health and wellbeing when using digital means and technologies.

Teaching media

- Outlines and infographics to organize learning and to illustrate relationships among various components of the educational materials
- Inquire learning (direct by questions), case study (real situations for the students to explore concepts in an authentic context), game based (as students make certain progress, they can earn badges).
- Practical exercises and case studies: quiz (self-assessment), forum (opinion), feedback (respond in forum section).
- The course documentation is written in EN/ RO/GE/GR.

C. COURSE OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the course is for trainees to understand their own rights and responsibilities as consumers in digital environments and the ways they are connected to the broader area of digital citizenship. The main objective is also related to the development of the relevant skills to respect and promote consumers rights and responsibilities.

More specific objectives include the development of certain knowledge and skills, so that trainees will:

- Understand the meaning and the importance of consumers rights and responsibilities in the digital world
- Be able to identify practices and behaviours which these rights or violate them
- Realize the key issues related to online safety and privacy when making purchases online
- Become familiar with the ways to counteract to incidents of violations of their rights as consumers
- Understand the connection and interdependence between online and offline consumer awareness

- Be sure on the available means and ways to report illegal or unethical practices by companies or advertisers
- Realize the necessity of respecting digital rights and fulfilling digital responsibilities and obligations as digital entrepreneurs
- Modify their online behaviours according to the newly acquired knowledge on consumer awareness in the digital world.

D. COURSE PLAN

Time	Detailed syllabus	Educational effects. Bloom's verbs	Instructional approach
Module 1	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Introduction to consumer awareness in digital environments- rights and responsibilities.</p> <p>Basic concepts to be introduced in this module are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -consumer rights and responsibilities - consumer awareness in online and offline environments - basic concepts related to consumer awareness, such as e-commerce, digital advertising, credit cards and online consumerism, secure transactions online, targeted advertising and misleading techniques. - how consumers can defend their rights and respect their responsibilities offline and online -online entrepreneurship 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain the connection between consumer awareness and digital citizenship - identify the connection between consumer rights in online and offline environments - match consumer rights with the responsibilities these rights entail - explain the necessity to respect consumer rights - recognize the positive effects of respecting consumer rights in digital environments - identify the most common concepts related to consumer awareness -give examples on how to protect consumers rights and report potential violations <p>SKILLS</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain the significance of consumer rights and responsibilities in digital environments - identify the areas where consumer rights and responsibilities relate to - categorize those consumer rights which are commonly violated or neglected - determine the interconnection between online and offline consumer rights and responsibilities - examine different aspects of online entrepreneurship 	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life problems and behaviours to guide students to acquire knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. The questions can be asked after the self- check quiz to promote dialogue and exchange of prior experiences in order to develop new skills related to consumer awareness - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - determine the quality of online advertising - evaluate misleading information contained in digital advertising. 	<p>promote experiential learning, cooperation and respect</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer demonstrates cases of online advertising and online entrepreneurship.
<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Class activity: Trainees take up a short quiz (developed by the trainer) to check existing skills and knowledge on consumer rights and responsibilities and consumer awareness. After completing the quiz, trainees share the results with the class and comment on the findings (face-to-face or online via forum). The trainer shows one of the following short videos on consumer rights and responsibilities: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T3vWwQEPL4&t=434s&ab_channel=lkenEdu which introduce viewers to these concepts. After watching the videos, the trainer can initiate a discussion on the connection between consumer rights in offline and online environments to assist trainees recognize similarities and differences.</p>	<p>PRACTICAL AREA</p> <p>Tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize and describe different consumer rights and responsibilities in online and offline environments - structure the content and ideas - identify potential violations of consumer rights - discuss the prevalence of consumer rights to all online interactions and transactions - consider their own practices related to their behaviours as online consumers - propose ways for the respect and protection of certain consumer rights, especially related to advertising and misleading practices <p>Analysis of statistical data on the digital habits of young people regarding their role as consumers of online products and services (country specific/ globally)</p>	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic using a quiz (already prepared) or a discussion - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings - presents and comments recent statistical data on the common violations of consumer rights - relates the concepts of consumer rights and responsibilities to everyday real-life behaviours - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions - selects and shows digital advertisements to discuss digital 	

	Moreover, the trainer can select two or three online advertisements to initiate a group discussion on the practices used to promote services and products online and on the enterprises behind them.		advertising and online entrepreneurship.
	DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees: - answer the questions posed at the forum - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting	TEACHING METHODS Forum
Module 2	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS e- commerce</p> <p>During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the concept of e-commerce and its distinct characteristics - key trends in e-commerce such as cross border purchases, the growth of mobile commerce and the role of social media in e-commerce - key benefits and risks of e-commerce for consumers - consumer protection as a precursor to consumer trust <p>(For extra material: http://www.oecd.org/digital/consumer/toolkit-</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand how consumers interact and transact in e-commerce - recognize the benefits of e-commerce - determine the risks related to e-commerce such as fraudulent and deceptive commercial Practices - explain the concerns about data use, privacy and security related to e-commerce - identify the role of social media in e-commerce <p>SKILLS</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - evaluate the key trends in e-commerce - take advantage of the opportunities e-commerce offers - compare fair and unfair business and advertising practices - determine how different risks of e-commerce can be avoided 	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life problems and behaviours to guide students to acquire knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote

	<p>for-protecting-digital-consumers.pdf)</p>		<p>experiential learning, cooperation and respect</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer presents the basic concepts related to e-commerce, including benefits and risks and initiates discussions
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Class activity: The trainer has prepared a short quiz to check the trainee’s knowledge on the issues covered in this Module. Trainees share their answers with the rest of the class and provide the trainer a clear idea on the trainees’ existing knowledge in order to build it up. The trainer can show the following video on e-commerce https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nxSDHBdsWqA&ab_channel=PeaSoupDigital which explains in simple terms what e-commerce is and its different dimensions. Then, a group discussion can take place on e-commerce, leading to the presentation of the benefits and the risks included in e-commerce. The trainer can also show a page taken from social media, including</p>	<p>Tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recognize the meaning and importance of e-commerce for consumers and enterprises - critically evaluate the information presented (on videos or presentations) to make conclusions on the characteristics of e-commerce - discuss on the benefits and risks of e-commerce - participate in the activities related to the role of social media in e-commerce <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply knowledge on e-commerce in their own consuming practices - determine whether a potential purchase is risky or not - evaluate the content of online advertising - choose the best way to protect their rights as consumers when they are violated 	<p>TEACHING METHODS The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic using a quiz or a discussion - synthesizes the trainees’ answers to conclude on common findings - presents and comments recent statistical data on the role of e-commerce in today’s societies and economies - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions - briefly presents laws, acts and regulations for the protection of consumers’ rights

	different types of advertisements to initiate a discussion on the role of social media in e-commerce		
	DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply Or A short quiz to check the acquisition of the relevant skills and knowledge	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees: - answer the questions posed at the forum/ quiz - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting	TEACHING METHODS Forum Or quiz
Module 3	THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Ethical considerations and risks During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed: - safety measures when shopping online - the use of credit cards when shopping online - the concept of "offers" which seem too good to be true - awareness of certain rights before making a purchase (for example, does the website offer a refund, money-back guarantee or some other method of reclamation?) - online business models which make consumers pay indirectly for the content/services they use and grant them none of the protection and rights - the importance of terms and conditions when making an online purchase - addiction to online sales	COGNITIVE AREA Trainees should be able to: - understand the basic ethical considerations and risks related to shopping online - compare different online payment services such as PayPal or Stripe - examine several online sales websites based on their trustworthiness - recognize ethical or unethical offers when shopping online - describe the connection between consumers rights and refund practices SKILLS - recognize examples of ethical or unethical practices when advertising or selling products online - determine the correct use of a credit card when shopping online - interpret behaviours related to the addiction to online sales - evaluate the terms and conditions of products sold and bought online - apply safety measures when shopping online	TEACHING METHOD - The trainer uses real-life problems and situations which can occur when shopping online to guide students to acquire relevant knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote experiential

<p>For extra material: https://rm.coe.int/digital-citizenship-education-handbook/168093586f</p>		<p>learning, cooperation and respect</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer presents the basic concepts related to certain rights and ethical issues when shopping online - The trainer can also use role-playing to activate trainees' interest and raise their awareness on the issue.
<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Class activity The trainer has prepared a short quiz to check the trainee's knowledge on the issues covered in this Module. Trainees share their answers with the rest of the class and provide the trainer a clear idea on the trainees' existing knowledge in order to build it up. The trainer can have the trainees choose an online payment service such as PayPal or Stripe and invite them to read through the terms and conditions of the platforms to determine the costs of the transactions and any other pertinent information that users should know – prior to purchase. This will provide an opportunity</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - respond to the quiz to reveal their existing knowledge, skills and experiences - participate in the discussions related to credit card use, online payment services, terms and conditions when shopping online - realize the ethical and safe ways to make online purchases - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply their existing knowledge to understand something new - evaluate different incidents and different responses to incidents regarding online payments, use of credit cards and violation of consumer rights - judge behaviours to conclude on whether they relate to addiction to online buying or not - self-confidence to buy products online 	<p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic using a quiz or a discussion - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings - presents and comments recent statistical data on issues such as credit cards and online shopping, terms and conditions, addiction to online purchases - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions - presents online payment services and online sales websites to

	<p>to discuss ethical issues related to online shopping.</p> <p>The trainer can also have the trainees examine several online sales websites. The trainer can pose the following questions in order to facilitate the acquisition of skills and knowledge on online selling practices:</p> <p>What are the top-selling products? What types of guarantees or refunds are provided? Does the online shopping site have distribution channels around the world? Does global distribution affect the top-selling products?</p> <p>Based on the answers the trainer can conclude on the current practices of selling and buying products online</p>		<p>promote trainees' critical thinking</p>
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION</p> <p>Forum posts and reply</p> <p>Or</p> <p>A short quiz to check the acquisition of the relevant skills and knowledge</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - answer the questions posed at the forum/ quiz - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting - research on the services available to report unethical behaviours when selling or buying online 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>Forum</p> <p>Or</p> <p>quiz</p>
Module 4	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS</p> <p>Online marketing</p> <p>During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed:</p>	<p>COGNITIVE AREA</p> <p>Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand and identify different strategies and techniques of online marketing 	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life examples of online marketing to guide students to

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - strategies and techniques of online marketing - similarities and differences between traditional marketing methods and online advertising - the format and structure of online advertisements - the different types of digital marketing and give examples of how some companies use those tools. (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Blogs, LinkedIn) - social media and online marketing - email marketing, internet advertising and search engine optimization - Youtubers, influencers and celebrities - concerns regarding online marketing, such as hidden costs, privacy issues and endorsements on social networking. <p>For extra material: https://mediasmarts.ca/lessonplan/online-marketing-kids-strategies-and-techniques-lesson</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explain similarities and differences between traditional marketing methods and online advertising - consider the format and structure of online advertisements - explain why social media use specific marketing strategies - determine the effects of email marketing - recognize the influence which Youtubers, influencers and celebrities exert on consumers through online marketing <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - evaluate online marketing techniques - distinguish between different types of online marketing - define risks behind online advertising - justify the online marketing techniques on social media - evaluate the role of Youtubers, influencers and celebrities in today's online marketing and advertising - match different types of online marketing to certain products and services - critically evaluate online advertisements 	<p>acquire relevant knowledge and skills.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote experiential learning, cooperation and respect - The trainer presents the basic concepts related to online marketing and digital advertising and initiates discussions on the issues - The trainer can also demonstrate digital advertisements to promote learning through comparison and experience
PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES Class activity		TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees:	TEACHING METHODS The trainer:

	<p>The trainer initiates a discussion on trainees' experiences of online marketing and digital ads to activate their interest and check their level of knowledge.</p> <p>The trainer can present online ads to promote a discussion on strategies used for online marketing such as prizes and contests, as well as the different strategies for different target groups.</p> <p>The trainer can demonstrate videos or sites to help students realize some ethical issues related to online advertising (such as advertising targeted at children).</p> <p>The trainer can divide trainees in groups, provide them with certain sites which are popular (such as YouTube, Twitter, Wikipedia) and ask each group to discuss and present the types, the techniques and the methods used for advertising in these sites, in order to promote trainees' awareness and expand their experiences.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - participate in the discussions related to online marketing and digital advertising - realize the ethical and safe to advertise products- and their opposite - discuss in small groups on popular sites which include advertisements - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apply their existing knowledge to understand something new regarding the advertisements they come across online - evaluate different incidents and different responses to incidents regarding online marketing - self-confidence to evaluate digital advertisements - creativity to find proper ways to advertise certain products and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic through a discussion on different types of online marketing - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings on the techniques of online marketing - presents and comments recent statistical data on online advertising, targeting specifically the group of youth - relates the concept of online marketing to everyday real-life situations and dilemmas - further clarifies concepts in case students pose questions - initiates and leads discussions to make conclusions on the issues discussed
	<p>DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply Or A short quiz to check the acquisition of the relevant skills and knowledge</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - answer the questions posed at the forum/ quiz - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics 	<p>TEACHING METHODS Forum Or quiz</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting - research on the services available to report improper online advertising 	
Module 5	<p>THEORETICAL SUBJECTS Online entrepreneurship</p> <p>During this module, the following topics will be presented and discussed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the meaning and the different forms of online entrepreneurship - the goods and services offered by the online entrepreneur, the methods of delivery, the terms and conditions, and other protection put it place to protect the consumer. - how entrepreneurial endeavours infringe consumer rights and responsibilities -how digital citizens are also acting as entrepreneurs, actively selling products and services to digital citizen consumers - the General Data Protection Regulation and online entrepreneurship - the general steps to be taken to become an online entrepreneur - key issues in online entrepreneurship 	<p>COGNITIVE AREA Trainees should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - understand the differences and similarities between online and offline entrepreneurship - detect the ways to become an online entrepreneur - realize the potential risks of becoming an online entrepreneur -identify the current trends of online entrepreneurship - present the importance of the General Data Protection Regulation <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - evaluate different online entrepreneurial initiatives - critically think on the advantages and disadvantages of becoming an online entrepreneur - determine the factors that differentiate a successful online entrepreneur and an unsuccessful one. 	<p>TEACHING METHOD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer uses real-life cases of online entrepreneurship to acquire relevant knowledge and skills. - The trainer uses activation techniques to help students connect their knowledge and experiences to the concepts presented in the module. - The trainer asks opening questions to engage students. - The trainer promotes collaboration, debates and group discussions to promote experiential learning, cooperation and respect - The trainer presents the basic concepts related to online entrepreneurship and initiates discussions on the responsibilities

			<p>which online entrepreneurs have</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The trainer can also use role-playing to activate trainees' interest and raise their awareness on the issue. - The trainer can show short videos of successful online entrepreneurs.
	<p>PRACTICAL TASKS/ EXERCISES</p> <p>Class activity</p> <p>The trainer asks trainees to provide different examples of online entrepreneurship initiatives.</p> <p>The trainer presents a series of online enterprises and initiates discussions on their success, quality, methodology, products, marketing, ethics, etc.</p> <p>The trainer discusses with trainees the prospects of young people becoming online entrepreneurs and the basic steps to be taken in order to achieve this.</p> <p>The trainer present good and bad practice examples of online entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>TASKS FOR TRAINEES</p> <p>Trainees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - respond to the presentation of examples of online entrepreneurship initiatives - support their choices in a logical manner - participate in the discussions to define and identify examples of successful online entrepreneurship initiatives - contemplate on the different steps to be taken to become an online entrepreneur - pose questions to clarify concepts - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting <p>SKILLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ability to make the connection between rights and responsibilities in the digital world and online entrepreneurship - apply their existing knowledge to understand something new related to online entrepreneurship - evaluate different online enterprises - develop the skills to become an online entrepreneur 	<p>TEACHING METHODS</p> <p>The trainer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - asks trainees to describe and write down what they already know about the topic through a discussion on online entrepreneurship initiatives - synthesizes the trainees' answers to conclude on common findings - presents and comments recent statistical data on online entrepreneurship, focusing on young people - relates the concept of online entrepreneurship to digital rights and responsibilities - further clarifies concepts in case

		- become empowered to pursue this sector	students pose questions
	DAILY EVALUATION Forum posts and reply Or A short quiz to check the acquisition of the relevant skills and knowledge	TASKS FOR TRAINEES Trainees: - answer the questions posed at the forum/ quiz - evaluate each other's knowledge on the new topics - receive further educational materials and an activity to prepare until the next meeting - research on the services available to support online entrepreneurship by youth	TEACHING METHODS Forum Or quiz

E. EXPLANATION OF THE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Measure individuals' progress: on completing the reading of each training module, the trainee will have the possibility to measure the individual progress through the questioning and application techniques. The self-evaluation test (module assessment) comprises individual tasks.

Certificate: In order to be awarded a certificate of completion for this course the student will be required to complete the tasks for all 5 modules and gain 5 badges. Collection of all badges will entitle the owner to receiving the certificate of course completion.

F. REFERENCES

<https://mediasmarts.ca/lessonplan/online-marketing-kids-strategies-and-techniques-lesson>
<https://rm.coe.int/digital-citizenship-education-handbook/168093586f>
<http://www.oecd.org/digital/consumer/toolkit-for-protecting-digital-consumers.pdf>
<https://www.incharge.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/Teachers-Guide-Lesson-Eleven.pdf>
<http://humanistburo.org/dosyalar/humdosya/Digital%20Citizenship%20and%20Your%20Child.pdf>
<https://entuity.com/understanding-digital-citizenship/>

Textbooks:

EN: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Consumer-Awareness.pdf>
RO: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Consumer-Awareness-RO.pdf>
GE: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Consumer-Awareness-DE.pdf>
GR: <https://trainingclub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DIGCIT-Consumer-Awareness-GR.pdf>
Moodle self-registration course: <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>

Conclusions

The Digital Citizenship Model Course is a valuable instrument for assisting trainers and educators to introduce and organize new training courses and enhance the existing training materials, to further deliver effective training to youth.

The model course is a one-stop-shop for all the ten areas related to digital citizenship, including Access and Inclusion, Learning and Creativity, Media and Information Literacy, Ethics and Empathy, Health and Wellbeing, e-Presence and Communications, Active Participation, Rights and Responsibilities, Privacy and Security, Consumer Awareness.

The model course exhibits all the necessary items and steps to help educators in training youth. These items include the course overview, the statement of training methodology, the course objectives, the course plan, the assessment system and references. The course cognitive areas and their associated levels of achievement were established using Bloom's taxonomy and cover various degrees of competence, from knowing and understanding all the way to creating new outputs.

The model course is a prerequisite for developing the course content, which may then be delivered to the target groups. In this regard, the model course may be used in two main scenarios either per se or with various degrees of change interventions to its methodology, objectives, and course plan or assessment system.

Most of the instructions included in the model course are just indicative. For example, the course designers have indicated the time for completing each area of learning in the course plan. However, the time may be adapted in accordance with the trainees' levels of understanding. Having adjusted the educational materials in such a manner to suit the trainees' level of understanding, the trainer shall draw the lesson plans based on the detailed syllabus.

The proposed lesson plans and other related items included in this model course were created within the DIGCIT project as an intermediate phase to developing a state of art course content. The course content is first developed in the form of textbooks and then published on the project website and other relevant platforms. The content is then transformed into massive online open courses hosted in the European non-formal e-learning platform <https://courses.trainingclub.eu/>. This platform was developed using Moodle. Moodle is a learning platform designed to provide educators, administrators and learners with a single robust, secure and integrated system to create personalised learning environments.

This e-learning platform hosts all the content and the proposed activities. Some of the activities are appropriate for reading and self-reflection, while others are designed to be facilitated in classrooms by trainers, requesting the active involvement of participants. Therefore, the course textbooks and e-learning platform may be used in the MOOC format, hybrid (with course participants following the content on the platform and carrying out various classroom activities) or face-to-face with trainers/facilitators.

Hence, in this paper, the authors created a flexible and multipurpose model course, which helps trainers to design and deliver online, hybrid and face-to-face training in the area of digital citizenship.

References

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